

Numerical Modeling of the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine in a Towing Tank

Master Thesis

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Eigenständigkeitserklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

Berlin, 29. August 2023

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Abstract

This thesis presents measures to reproduce the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine (UBeRT) inside QBLADE. A simplified structural model of the turbine is derived to allow for analytical and code-to-code validation and verification. QBLADE's PROJECT CHRONO library is employed to solve the multi-body representation of the turbine. The results fit the prediction of the analytical and the high-fidelity model used for the code-to-code comparison reasonably well. The aeroelastic response throughout the operational regime of the turbine is assessed and searched for potentially dangerous operating points. The side-side and fore-aft nacelle accelerations do not indicate unstably amplified mode shapes of the turbine. Acceleration ramps of the rotational speed and the inflow velocity to crucial operating points are simulated. The correlated loads on critical components are monitored and, where necessary, adapted factors of safety are derived. From the numerical assessment, the turbine's structural integrity can be guaranteed. Additionally, the wake of the turbine model is simulated employing a lifting line method to generate a sample data set at two operating points. Appropriate post-processing algorithms are developed and tested. Despite not being verified against high-fidelity simulations and/or experiments, the extracted data resembles general features of wakes of modern-day horizontal axis wind turbines. Averaged velocity profiles and numerical noise metrics are considered at various downstream positions to gain insights into the development of the wake of the UBeRT. In the future, the UBeRT test rig will be used to measure tip vortex instabilities employing stereoscopic underwater particle image velocimetry. Once validated experimentally, the numerical model will serve as a digital twin. Promising velocimetry planes can be derived, controllers can be tuned, and parameter studies on blade tip devices can be conducted.

Kurzfassung

In dieser Arbeit werden Maßnahmen vorgestellt zur Modellierung der Underwater Berlin Research Turbine (UBeRT) in QBLADE. Ein vereinfachtes Strukturmodell der Turbine wird analytisch und mittels "code-to-code"-Vergleichs validiert. Das Mehrkörpermodell wird mit QBLADE's PROJECT CHRONO Bibliothek gelöst und untersucht. QBLADE ist innerhalb der durch die unterschiedlichen Modellierungsansätze bedingten Grenzen ausreichend gut in der Lage, die Vorhersagen der Referenzmodelle zu reproduzieren. Aeroelastische Interaktionen werden im gesamten Betriebsbereich der Turbine bewertet und nach potenziell gefährlichen Betriebspunkten gesucht. Die "side-side" und "fore-aft" Gondelbeschleunigungen deuten auf keine instabil verstärkten Modalformen im Betrieb der Turbine hin. Beschleunigungsrampen für die Rotationsgeschwindigkeit und die ungestörte Anströmgeschwindigkeit zu kritischen Betriebspunkten werden in simuliert. Die damit verbundenen Belastungen kritischer Komponenten werden überwacht und, wenn nötig, angepasste Sicherheitsfaktoren abgeleitet. Die numerische Untersuchung weist die strukturelle Integrität der Turbine im gesamten Parameterbereich nach. Zusätzlich wird der Nachlauf der Turbine mit einer "lifting line"-Methode an zwei Betriebspunkten simuliert, um einen Musterdatensatz zu erzeugen. Geeignete Nachbearbeitungsalgorithmen werden entwickelt und getestet. Obwohl die extrahierten Daten nicht anhand von hochauflösenden Simulationen und/oder Experimenten verifiziert wurden, ähneln sie in allgemeinen Merkmalen den Nachläufen moderner horizontalachsigen Windkraftanlagen. Gemittelte Geschwindigkeitsprofile und eine Metrik zur Quantifizierung des numerischen Rauschens werden an verschiedenen stromabwärts gelegenen Positionen betrachtet, um Einblicke in die Entwicklung des Nachlaufs der UBeRT zu gewinnen. In Zukunft werden am UBeRT-Prüfstand Spitzenwirbelinstabilitäten mit stereoskopischer Particle-Image-Velocimetry unter Wasser vermessen. Nach der experimentellen Validierung wird das numerische Modell als "digital twin" dienen. Vielversprechende Ebenen zur Geschwindigkeitsmessung können abgeleitet, Regler können getestet und es können Parameterstudien zu vielversprechenden Flügelspitzengeometrien durchgeführt werden.

Author's Note

The present thesis is the second master's thesis of the author, Sascha Krumbein, in the project "Dynamics and Destabilisation of Helical Vortices" with the Institute for Fluid Mechanics and Technical Acoustics. The first thesis with the title *Design of a horizontal axis wind turbine for experimental investigation in a large water towing tank* was submitted on April 27th, 2023, and concluded his Master's degree in Mechanical Engineering from the Technische Universität Berlin. Throughout the thesis at hand, the first master's thesis is referenced as follows: MT1 [\[1\]](#)

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1 Research Motivation

Modern-day horizontal axis wind turbines (HAWTs) consist of three (sometimes two) blades, the nacelle, and the tower. The tangential force distribution f_T along the blades, generated from aerodynamic lift f_L and drag f_D forces per unit width, imposes a torque \mathcal{Q} on the main shaft. The drive train includes a hub, the turbine shaft, often a gearbox, the generator and additional components, such as the control system and a transformer [2]. The normal force distribution f_N on the blades results in an integral force collinear to the turbine's main axis, called thrust \mathcal{T} . Wind turbines operate inside the atmospheric boundary layer (Figure 1.1). A turbulent velocity field $\vec{U}(\vec{x},t)$ (e.g., $[U \ V \ W]_i(\vec{x},t)\mathbf{e}_i$) at position \vec{x} (e.g., $[x \ y \ z]_i\mathbf{e}_i$) and time t , can be decomposed, utilizing REYNOLDS' decomposition (Equation (1.1)), into a suitably averaged mean flow field $\overline{\vec{U}}(\vec{x},t)$ and turbulent fluctuations $\vec{u}(\vec{x},t)$ [3].

$$\vec{U}(\vec{x},t) = \overline{\vec{U}}(\vec{x},t) + \vec{u}(\vec{x},t) \quad (1.1)$$

The averaged¹ component of the atmospheric boundary layer can be preliminarily assumed to be solely dependent on the vertical coordinate, i.e., z in \mathbf{e}_z direction, and the time t . Hence, the inflow velocity far upstream² of the turbine can be sufficiently characterized by $\overline{U}_\infty(z,t)$. For turbines of small rotor diameters compared to the length scales of the atmospheric boundary layer, the undisturbed inflow velocity becomes constant along z , i.e., $\overline{U}_\infty(z,t) = \overline{U}_\infty(t)$. In steady conditions³, $\overline{U}_\infty(t)$ reduces to \overline{U}_∞ [4–6].

Due to the momentum transferred from the flow field to the rotor, the thrust causes the overall fluid velocity just upstream and downstream of the turbine to be smaller. The velocity deficit can be as high as 20% [7], compared to the undisturbed inflow velocity ($\overline{U}_\infty(x_1) > \overline{U}(r,x_i)$, $i \in \{2,3,4\}$, Figure 1.2). The conservation of mass requires the expansion of the fluid flow due to the velocity reduction [4, 8]. The entirety of reduced velocity is called *wake*. It is typically grouped into three distinct sections: the *near-wake*, the *transitional-* or *intermediate-wake*, and the *far-wake* (Figure 1.2). In the near-wake, the turbine's characteristic and operational point heavily influence the occurring velocity field. That

¹($\overline{\cdot}$)

²i.e., undisturbed at ∞ location

³ $\partial/\partial t = 0$

Figure 1.1: Averaged undisturbed atmospheric boundary layer $\overline{U}_\infty(z,t)$ with turbulent fluctuations $u(z,t)$ based on [2]. Decomposition from [3]. Wind turbine components and definition of rotor radius R , diameter D , angular velocity Ω , and blade phase angle ϑ (\mathbf{e} depicts unity vectors).

Figure 1.2: Time-averaged turbine wake topology and taxonomy reproduced from [8, 10]. Characteristic time-averaged velocity profiles displayed at different downstream positions of an actuator disc imposing a thrust \mathcal{T} onto an undisturbed fluid flow ($\bar{U}_\infty(x_1)$). Outer shear layer boundary indicated by black line. Transitional wake starts where toroidal shear layer reaches rotor axis. Transition is characterized by the development of the far-wake velocity profile.

is, distinguishable turbine-dependent flow patterns of various kinds are clearly apparent. Vortices shed at the nacelle, the tower, the blade tips, the roots, and from stalled conditions on the blade surfaces form, are convected, and interact with one another and the turbulent inflow field [8]. At the edge of the near-wake towards the ambient flow, a toroidal shear-layer emerges, accompanied by an increased degree of turbulence of up to 130 to 150 % [9]. The wake expands through turbulent entrainment. The downstream location, where the shear-layers merge, defines the termination of the near-wake region. Thereafter, the recovery of the velocity deficit is initiated. [5, 10, 11]. Alternatively, Sørensen et al. [12] characterize the end of the near-wake by the onset of unstably growing instabilities immanent in the tip vortices. The transitional-wake is governed by the transformation of the near-wake, with the aerodynamic signature of each blade, to the (roughly GAUSSIAN) far-wake [2]. Spectral peaks in the generated turbulence attributed to rotor-specific frequencies and wavenumbers disappear [9, 10, 13]. In the far-wake, the velocity deficit vanishes monotonically within 5 to 15D. The axial component of the fluctuations converges to the ambient level. Wake effects can be measured up to 20D downstream of a HAWT [7].

In modern-day grid-type wind parks (Figure 1.3), the side-by-side and row-to-row spacing is typically of the order of 5D and 10D, respectively [14]. Hence, downstream turbines are (partially) shadowed by the wakes of turbines upstream, which causes the largest share of annual energy production losses [15]. Mikkelsen et al. [16] found that downstream turbines produce 40 to 60 % of the power compared to the foremost turbines. Burton [5] reports up to 23 % in annual energy production losses at the Lillgrund Pilot Project site, attributed to wake effects. Barthelmie et al. [17] show power production drops of up to 60 % for certain wind directions, causing an annual energy production reduction of 10 to 20 %. The energy production losses are accompanied by increased fatigue loads on downstream turbines. Frandsen [2] found that the equivalent loads are directly proportional to the standard deviation of the wind speed fluctuations. Dahlberg et al. [18] measured 300 % increased turbulence degrees at downstream turbine positions in the Alsvik wind farm, caused by the wake effects of upstream turbines. 300 % enlarged blade flapwise moment variations resulted. Mikkelsen et al. [16] and Chacón et al. [19] reported agreeing magnitudes of 200 to 300 %. Figure 1.3 shows the Horns Rev 2 wind park off the coast of Denmark. The combination of oversaturated air, turbulent fluctuations imposed by the wind turbine rotors, and the resulting varying pressure field causes the generation of microscale water droplets. Assuming that the fog is a suitable indicator, the (partial) shadowing of downstream turbines and the wake expansion become visible.

The relevance of wake effects for the efficacy of wind parks justifies the vast research interest. Numerous analytical, numerical, and experimental approaches were followed over the years, focusing on

Figure 1.3: Visible wind turbine wakes in large-scale wind park (Horns Rev 2) from Dong Energy/Bel Air Aviation Denmark - Helicopter Services (2017).

various wake-related topics. Among them, methods of exciting the wake to induce preliminary or accelerated shear-layer breakdown and wake recovery attracted a lot of attention. The toroidal shear-layer, generated by the vortex helix emanating from the blade tips, shields the inner wake region and prevents the re-energizing of the velocity deficit [11]. Yet, the unstable nature of the tip vortex helix represents an attractive starting point for developing efficient methods to reduce the range of the wake. Widnall [20] predicted analytically three dominating instability modes of a helical vortex filament: the *short-wave*, the *low-wavenumber*, and the *mutual-inductance* or *pairing* instability for small helical pitch. Gupta et al. [21] extended Widnall’s findings by investigating multiple interdigitated helical vortex filaments. Again, the mutual-inductance instability was identified and correlated to the highest level of instability, i.e., the most sensitive to 3D perturbations. Bhagwat et al. [22] conducted an extensive numerical analysis of helicopters in hover and axial flight. They found that numerical errors in their simulation can artificially excite the mutual-inductance mode, proving yet again its sensitivity. The early-stage research always found unconditional instability of the tip vortex helix [20–25]. However, this was contradicted by real-world visualizations of the phenomenon. Figure 1.4 summarizes examples of experimental campaigns that prove the strong coherence and stability of the vortex systems behind wind turbine rotors. Figure 1.4a shows the near-wake of a full-scale wind turbine, visualized by snowflake voids. The field of view is perpendicular to the rotor plane. Occurring periodic structures can be attributed to distinct origins, such as the tip vortices and the vortices shed from the tower. Figures 1.4b and 1.4c depict experiments under controlled conditions. In both cases, the helix is visualized by adding tracer particles to the vortex cores. The campaigns revealed a stable helix for at least one rotor diameter. The first ones to find and investigate a stable analytical representation of the problem were Okulov et al. [29]. They combined N_b tip vortices with a prescribed vorticity field and a root vortex. The analysis of the resulting system revealed the stabilization of the tip vortex helix by the underlying vorticity. Meanwhile, Leweke et al. [30] ran various water-tunnel experiments to understand the reason for the instability cascades in straight vortex pairs.

Figure 1.4: Examples of visualized instantaneous near-wake structures. **a)** Coherent patterns visualized using snowflake voids in the near-wake of a full-scale turbine, including tip vortices, root vortex, nacelle vortex, and the tower shadow. Taken from [26]. **b)** Tip vortex helix of a two-bladed wind turbine visualized using smoke, emanated from the blade tip. Vortex perturbations and breakdown visible, induced by the turbine tower. Experiments on full-scale NREL turbine carried out in the NASA-Ames wind tunnel. Taken from [27]. **c)** Dye visualizations of a helical tip vortex. Water flume experiments on model-scale helicopter rotor in slow ascent. Taken from [28].

They identified the instability of elliptical streamlines to 3D perturbations (*elliptical* instability) as vital for the unstable growth of perturbations in parallel vortex structures (Figure 1.5a). Their work was extended by several campaigns on different aspects of straight vortex pairs [31–34]. Meunier et al. [35, 36] summarized and generalized their findings for 3D systems and merging phenomena. An extensive review of research on elliptical instabilities is given in [37]. With the same setup, Leweke et al. [38] investigated helically intertwined filaments, the emerging vortex patterns, and their dynamics. They induced the pairing of adjacent vortices and, among others, triggered the onset of short-wave instabilities by modulating the rotational speed of the single-bladed rotor. The former group displacements of the whole vortex with minimal effect on the internal core structure. The latter refer to perturbations that arise inside the vortex core with wavelengths of the order of the core diameter [39]. At the bottom of the short-wave instability, they discovered again an elliptical instability and additionally a *curvature* instability, as described by [40–42]. The non-linear interactions between the short and long wave instabilities cause a particular rapid and permanent breakdown of the rotor wake (Figure 1.5c). Quaranta et al. [43] and [44] measured the occurring velocity field utilizing particle image velocimetry (PIV) and reproduced the findings of Leweke et al. An extensive summary of the inherent dynamics of elliptical and curvature instabilities can be found in [42, 45, 46]. Ivanell et al. [47] conducted computational fluid mechanics (CFD) simulations of a three-bladed wind turbine rotor, focusing on the emerging tip vortex instabilities. By superimposing 3D perturbations of varying period and wavelength near the blade tips, they searched for particularly sensitive responses to certain frequencies. The non-dimensional growth rate of the pairing instability was found to be $\pi/2$. This was later verified [12, 38]. Critical spatial growth of out-of-phase displacement perturbations occurs for wavenumbers κ equal to odd multiples of $1/2$. κ is defined as the number of wavelengths in one helix turn.

In recent times, the understanding of the fundamental mechanism of unstable dynamics in helical vortex system has been used to assess their applicability to (wind turbine) rotors for inducing accelerated wake breakdown. Brocklehurst et al. [48] reviewed several helicopter blade tip designs, focusing on their influence on the creation of the tip vortex helix. Additionally, they summarized the influence of geometric tip modifications on the overall performance of helicopter rotors. First, Buffo et al. [49] and later Schröder et al. [28, 39, 50], conducted extensive water-tunnel measurements of wing tip designs, utilizing PIV. The setup represented helicopter rotors in slow ascent. The influence of a perpendicular fin placed on the pressure side of a single-bladed rotor was investigated. The creation of a secondary vortex destabilized the tip vortex helix significantly by inducing chaotic merging events (Figure 1.5b). Abraham et al. [26] studied the applicability of three-bladed asymmetric rotors for triggering the pairing instability. The rotor was designed to resemble wind turbines. Accelerated wake breakdown by inducing leapfrogging and pairing events was observed, especially for rotor configurations that impose a positive strain field. The approach appears to be promising for exciting wind turbine wakes. Marten et al. [51] conducted lifting line free vortex wake (LLFVW) simulations of small- and full-scale HAWTs. They excited the tip vortex by utilizing trailing edge flaps and prescribing an oscillatory motion. Critical excitation frequencies were identified for inducing the destabilization of the wake. The authors showed a significant shift of the wake breakdown closer to the rotor plane for increasing excitation amplitudes. Leweke et al. [38] identified the efficacy of short-wave modes for inducing a particularly accelerated wake recovery, as can be seen in Figure 1.5c. Currently, the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine (UBeRT) is under construction at the Technische Universität Berlin (Chapter 2). The three-bladed HAWT model will be used to measure wake instabilities utilizing stereoscopic underwater PIV. The aforementioned methods and strategies will be implemented and tested for their applicability at comparably high spanwise REYNOLDS numbers approaching $Re = 700\,000$. The experimental campaigns will be used to generate data sets for validating high-fidelity detached-eddy simulations carried out at the Universität Stuttgart. The combination will enable the testing of the implications of the most promising designs on full-scale turbines and turbine arrays.

This thesis explains the numerical modeling of the UBeRT test rig inside the QBLADE software, developed at Technische Universität Berlin. The research objective is:

Figure 1.5: **a)** Visualization of two co-rotating straight vortices with finite vortex core. Mutual inductance creates strain field resulting in elliptical deformation of the circular streamlines. Velocity field is unstable. Picture taken before non-linear vortex merging occurs. Taken from [35]. **b)** Dye visualizations of a helical tip vortex. Water flume experiments on model-scale helicopter rotor in slow ascent. Secondary vortex created by a perpendicular fin on the pressure side near the blade tip. Baseline setup in Figure 1.4c. Topology of the tip vortex helix changed significantly. Taken from [28]. **c)** One-bladed rotor immersed in water flow including visualization of the tip vortex helix using dye. Short-wave (i.e., elliptical or curvature) instabilities induced vortex pairing. Combination leads to rapid and violent wake breakdown. Taken from [38].

Research Objective

To generate a validated numerical model of the UBeRT structure, including the turbine and the tower, utilizing code-to-code comparisons and analytical considerations.

Chapter 2 defines the main aspects of the UBeRT design. Chapter 3 introduces aspects of the fundamental theory of the methods. The numerical model, including the aerodynamic and structural properties of the turbine, is explained in Chapter 4. Analytical and code-to-code validations are conducted. Relevant simulation studies for ensuring the safe operation of the turbine during the experimental campaigns are analyzed in Chapter 5. The thesis ends with a conclusion of the acquired findings (Chapter 6) and an outlook, including additional issues raised throughout the thesis (Chapter 7).

2 The Underwater Berlin Research Turbine (UBeRT)

The UBeRT is a $N_b = 3$ bladed, $D = 1.3$ m HAWT model, which is currently being manufactured at the Technische Universität Berlin (Figure 2.7). The following sections summarize key aspects of the turbine necessary for setting up an accurate model. The plots and findings are partly taken from MT1 [1]. Table 2.1 contains the ambient conditions, the parameter regime of the test rig, and details of the design. The parameter set is used as input to the numerical model, in addition to the airfoil polars.

The testing of the turbine will be conducted in the large water towing tank of the Technische Universität Berlin (Figure 2.8). The tank consists of a basin with a length of 250 m, a width of 8.1 m and two different depths. The first 60 m are 3.4 m, the remaining 190 m are 5.2 m deep. Blockage ratios of 4.82 % and 3.2 % are yielded. The three-bladed turbine will be submerged to a depth of 2.5 m and centered in the basin to minimize free surface and tank wall effects. A 17 m long preparation section with a width of 2.1 m and a depth of 2.4 m complements the towing tank. A 25 t carriage, driven by eight 55.5 kW direct current motors, moves parallel to the water surface on two rails. The measurement platform allows for vertical and lateral traversability. The platform is dimensioned to withstand 20 kN of vertical and 10 kN of longitudinal loading. The forward velocity of the carriage ranges from 0.125 to 12.5 m s^{-1} , the backward velocity ranges from -10 to -0.125 m s^{-1} . Accelerations between -3 to 1 m s^{-2} are possible.

2.1 Turbine description

The rotor blades of the turbine are derived from the SG6040 low-REYNOLDS number airfoil [52]. The airfoil is selected from a range of low-speed HAWT airfoils and qualified using a load study focusing on the maximum deflection and minimum factor of safety (MT1 [1]). The airfoil has a maximum thickness of $d_{\max} = 16$ % at chord location $\eta_d = 35.2$ % and a maximum camber of $f_{\max} = 2.53$ % at $\eta_f = 58.79$ %. Figures 2.1a until 2.1c show the airfoils from XFOIL simulations [53]. The simulations are conducted without tripping for a thickened version of the SG6040, where $\Delta = 0.01c$ is the trailing edge (TE) thickness. The thickening function $\zeta_t = \zeta \pm 0.5\eta\Delta/c$ is used with $0 \leq \eta \leq c$. Points of the pressure side are transformed by (+), suction side points by (-). The SG6040 profile is designed for constituting the root sections of wind turbine blades of small HAWTs, hence the high maximum

Figure 2.1: Airfoil polars of the thickened SG6040 profile from XFOIL simulations without tripping. a) Lift coefficient C_L , b) drag coefficient C_D , and c) pitch moment coefficient C_M .

Table 2.1: Ambient conditions, operational regime, and finalized overall dimensions of the UBeRT.

Quantity	Symbol	Range/Value	
<i>Ambient Conditions</i>			
Gravity	g	9.81 m s^{-1}	
Tank temperature	θ	$20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	
Depth of submergence	H_{des}	2.5 m	
Fluid density	ϱ	998.22 kg m^{-3}	
Kinematic viscosity	ν	$10^{-6} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
Atmospheric pressure	\bar{P}_{at}	1.01325 bar	
Ambient pressure	\bar{P}_{∞}	1.258 bar	
Water vapor pressure	\bar{P}_{v}	2338 Pa	
<i>Operational Range</i>			
Inflow velocity	\bar{U}_{∞}	$0.5 \text{ to } 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$	
TSR	λ	$4 \text{ to } 10$	
Angular velocity	Ω	$3.08 \text{ to } 23.08 \text{ s}^{-1}$	
RPM range	n	$29.4 \text{ to } 220.4 \text{ min}^{-1}$	
<i>Blade Design Parameters</i>			
Airfoil	Thickened SG6040, $\Delta = 0.01c$		
REYNOLDS number	Re_{des}	$400\,000$	
TSR	λ_{des}	7	
AoA	α_{des}	1°	
<i>Turbine</i>			
Nacelle length	L_{N}	$1.56 \text{ m} = 1.2D$	
Nacelle diameter	$D_{\text{N},1}$	$0.13 \text{ m} = 0.1D$	$x_{\text{N}} = 0.082 \text{ to } 0.458 \text{ m}$
	$D_{\text{N},2}$	$0.155 \text{ m} \approx 0.12D$	$x_{\text{N}} = 0.575 \text{ to } 1.2 \text{ m}$
<i>Tower</i>			
Tower length	L_{T}	4.961 m	
Tower section 1	$D_{\text{T},1}$	0.112 m	$z_{\text{T}} = 0 \text{ to } 0.829 \text{ m}$
	$d_{\text{T},1}$	0.09 m	
Tower section 2	$D_{\text{T},2}$	0.2 m	$z_{\text{T}} = 0.829 \text{ to } 3.302, 3.502 \text{ to } 4.668 \text{ m}$
	$d_{\text{T},2}$	0.18 m	
Tower section 3	$D_{\text{T},3}$	0.12 m	$z_{\text{T}} = 3.302 \text{ to } 3.502 \text{ m}$
Tower section 4	$D_{\text{T},4}$	0.135 m	$z_{\text{T}} = 4.668 \text{ to } 4.961 \text{ m}$
Bearing locations	$z_{\text{T},\text{ub}}$	4.961 m	
	$z_{\text{T},\text{lb}}$	3.402 m	
Hinge location	$z_{\text{T},\text{H}}$	3.129 m	
Stiffening knot	$z_{\text{T},\text{K}}$	1.334 m	

thickness. The large distance of the maximum thickness and camber from the leading edge (LE) causes comparatively high rear-loading of the airfoil, visible in the moment coefficient (Figure 2.1c). The SG6040 reaches a maximum lift coefficient of approximately $C_{L,\max} = 1.5$ at AoA $\alpha = 15^\circ$. For $\text{Re} = 10^5$ and moderate AoAs, the formation of a laminar separation bubble is apparent in the polars. Increased drag C_D (Figure 2.1b), reduced lift C_L (Figure 2.1a), and reduced pitching moment C_M (Figure 2.1c) between $\alpha = -2$ to 8° can be seen.

From SCHMITZ's blade design formulas [4, 54, 55], the pitch β and chord c distribution of the UBeRT blades are derived (Equations (2.1)).

$$\beta_S(r) = \frac{2}{3} \arctan\left(\frac{R}{r\lambda_{\text{des}}}\right) - \alpha_{\text{des}} \quad (2.1a)$$

$$c_S(r) = \frac{16\pi r}{N_b C_L(\alpha_{\text{des}}, \text{Re}_{\text{des}})} \sin^2\left(\frac{1}{3} \arctan\left(\frac{R}{r\lambda_{\text{des}}}\right)\right) \quad (2.1b)$$

The following design parameters are used: TSR $\lambda_{\text{des}} = 7$, AoA $\alpha_{\text{des}} = 1^\circ$, number of blades $N_b = 3$, REYNOLDS number $\text{Re}_{\text{des}} = 4 \times 10^5$, and lift coefficient $C_L = 0.56$. The resulting curves are plotted in Figure 2.2. For $0 \leq r \leq 130$ mm, the blade contours deviate from SCHMITZ's design for structural reasons. Dashed lines indicate the theoretical path; solid lines indicate the realized one. Figure 2.2b depicts the bound circulation along the blade at various inflow and operational conditions. Especially for $\lambda = 7$, the circulation is rather constant along the radius. This causes the vorticity to trail mostly at the blade tip and root, yielding strong, concentrated tip vortices. The curves are derived from blade element momentum (BEM) simulations (Section 3.1) with the numerical tool QBLADE (Section 3.4). The design AoA is chosen to assure large margins towards positive and negative AoAs before stall. Moreover, operating the airfoil at small AoAs reduces the pressure peaks imposed by the profile. Hence, the risk of blade surface cavitation is minimized. Additionally, defining a suboptimal design AoA leads to a reduced lift coefficient $C_L(\alpha_{\text{des}})$, yielding an enlarged blade chord (Equation 2.1b).

$$\text{Re}(r) := \frac{\bar{q}(r)c(r)}{\nu} \quad (2.2)$$

Equation (2.2) defines the chordwise REYNOLDS number, with q as the absolute inflow velocity and

Figure 2.2: a) Final pitch β and chord c distributions over radius r . \cdots SCHMITZ's blade design from Equations 2.1. Differences near blade root attributed to geometric transition. b) Bound circulation at various inflow velocities \bar{U}_∞ and TSRs λ . --- $\bar{U}_\infty = 0.5$ m/s⁻¹, --- $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5$ m/s⁻¹, --- $\lambda = 4$, --- $\lambda = 7$, --- $\lambda = 10$. Color-code for dashed curves accordingly.

Figure 2.3: Pressure side view of the final blade contour with highlighted blade sections of the Underwater Berlin Research Turbine. $L_{bl} = 583$ mm, $R = 650$ mm. — Blade section made from interpolated airfoils. Pitch axis is equal to quarter-chord line over majority of the blade. Transition towards center chord location is realized in interpolated section.

chord c at location r , divided by the kinematic viscosity ν . Thus, the increased blade chord benefits the spanwise REYNOLDS number, and the gained insights become more applicable to full-scale HAWTs.

Figure 2.3 shows the pressure side of the UBeRT blade. Interpolated profiles are implemented near the blade root to assure a smooth transition towards a circular cross-section (highlighted section). The blade's pitch axis is defined by the quarter-chord locations of the blade sections for the majority of the blade. After generating the solid body inside SOLIDWORKS, the resulting blade is compared against the original thickened SG6040 airfoil at various locations. Deviations between sections near the blade tip and at positions of large geometric gradients are quantified and qualified regarding their influence on the aerodynamic performance. The blade is proven to resemble the design targets satisfactorily. Deviations and their estimated effect on the polars are minimal. The outboard section of the blade is exchangeable without the need to manufacture the entire blade anew. Thereby, extensive parameter studies on different blade tip geometries are enabled. The joints and centering holes will be smoothed and finely sanded after assembling the blades.

Figures 2.4 summarize the integral properties of the UBeRT rotor, derived from BEM simulations inside QBLADE. A range of inflow velocities is visualized. $\bar{U}_\infty = 2$ m s⁻¹ is used to derive the highlighted design conditions for critical turbine components, although the test rig will only be operated up to $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5$ m s⁻¹. This leads to overdimensioned components such as the bearings, the coupling, the main shaft, and the tower. Additional safety margins are achieved. Figures 2.4a until 2.4c show the dimensional turbine characteristics of power \mathcal{P} , torque \mathcal{Q} , and thrust \mathcal{T} as functions of RPM n . A maximum power output of $\mathcal{P}_{max} = 2.35$ kW is generated at $n_{\mathcal{P}} = 176$ min⁻¹, which has to be transmitted by the electrical components of the drive train. The maximum torque of $\mathcal{Q}_{max} = 186$ Nm at $n_{\mathcal{Q}} = 102$ min⁻¹ and thrust $\mathcal{T}_{max} = 2.22$ kN at $n_{\mathcal{T}} = 264$ min⁻¹ have to be counteracted by the main shaft, the bearings, the blade roots, and the tower. Figures 2.4d until 2.4f show the dimensionless representations of the turbine characteristics. λ is the TSR, defined in Equation (2.3).

$$\lambda := \frac{\Omega R}{\bar{U}_\infty} \quad (2.3)$$

The coefficients are influenced by the undisturbed inflow velocity. Especially towards the lower end of the parameter regime (Table 2.1), the curves appear to be significantly altered. The turbine reaches a maximum power coefficient $C_{\mathcal{P},max} = 0.44$ at $\lambda = 6$. The power $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ and the torque coefficient $C_{\mathcal{Q}}$ are related by $C_{\mathcal{P}} = \lambda C_{\mathcal{Q}}$. Therefore, the maximum torque coefficient is shifted to lower TSRs, where $C_{\mathcal{Q},max} = 0.11$ at $\lambda = 3.5$. The thrust coefficient $C_{\mathcal{T}}$ peaks at $C_{\mathcal{T},max} = 0.84$ at $\lambda = 9$.

Figures 2.5 visualize several dynamic properties of the UBeRT test rig throughout the defined parameter regime. The figures are superimposed by a prediction of blade surface cavitation. The obtained contour is included in every parameter plot. Operational points beyond the solid curve impose a

Figure 2.4: Aerodynamic performance characteristics of the UBeRT derived from QBLADE's BEM module. **a)** Power \mathcal{P} , **b)** torque \mathcal{Q} , and **c)** thrust \mathcal{T} over rotational speed n . Maximum values highlighted. Coefficients for **d)** power C_P , **e)** torque C_Q , and **f)** thrust C_T over tip speed ratio λ . Tow carriage velocity \bar{U}_∞ in m s^{-1} as a parameter.

Figure 2.5: Resulting parameter space of the UBeRT test rig, including a risk assessment for the onset of cavitation. Design angle of attack set to $\alpha_{\text{des}} = 1^\circ$. Pressure field for cavitation risk assessment derived at $\text{Re} = 4 \times 10^5$. $-C_{p,\text{max}} = 0.8876$. **a)** Absolute inflow velocity $\bar{q}(R) = \bar{U}_\infty \sqrt{\lambda^2 + 1/9}$. The axial induction factor at the blade tip of $a(R) = 1/3$ is extracted from QBLADE. **b)** Operational point dependent REYNOLDS number $\text{Re}(R)$ and **c)** cavitation number $\sigma(R)$ at the blade tip.

significant risk of cavitation. The theoretical prediction is based on the maximum negative pressure coefficient C_p of the SG6040 profile. XFOIL estimates $-C_{p,\max} = 0.8876$ at $\alpha = 1^\circ$. Comparing the cavitation number σ with the maximum negative pressure coefficient yields a threshold condition where surface cavitation must be expected (Figure 2.5c). However, the assessment is derived from two-dimensional considerations. Due to the highly three-dimensional nature of the flow around the blade, the accuracy of the prediction method is questionable. Experiments of various pitch, inflow velocities, and TSR configurations must be conducted to clarify the issue. Figure 2.5a shows the absolute inflow velocity at the blade tip, derived from $\bar{q}(R) = \bar{U}_\infty \sqrt{\lambda^2 + 1/9}$. The inflow velocity increases monotonically towards the upper right end of the parameter regime. Absolute velocities at the blade tips, ranging from $\bar{q}(R) = 1.5$ to 20 m s^{-1} are estimated. The REYNOLDS number, derived from Equation (2.2) at the blade tip ($r = R$), follows the same monotonic trend as the absolute inflow velocity. Minimum and maximum values of $\text{Re}_{\min} = 6.5 \times 10^4$ and $\text{Re}_{\max} = 8.7 \times 10^5$ are yielded.

Figure 2.6 shows a sectional view of the model turbine. Crucial drive train and turbine components are highlighted. The turbine contains a 7.5 kW servo-planetary-gear motor with a gear ratio of 12 : 1. The angular position and rotational velocity of the drive are resolved using an absolute encoder. The servo motor is coupled to the main shaft employing a metal bellows coupling with a rated maximum torque of 200 Nm. The partially hollow main shaft rests on a fixed-floating pair of self-aligning roller bearings. Between the bearings, a 24-channel slip ring is incorporated for transforming the blade root bending

Figure 2.6: Section view of the UBeRT including identifiers for main drive train components. (1) Drive unit, including holding break, encoder, servo motor with planetary gear. (2) Three-component thrust gauge. (3) Metal bellows coupling. (4) Self-aligning roller bearing (floating). (5) Slip ring. (6) Self-aligning roller bearing (fixed). (7) Root bending strain gauge amplifiers.

moment (BRBM) signals, acquired in the rotating coordinate system, into the non-rotating system. The three blades are screwed to the hub and positioned to define the blade pitch by employing centering pins.

The mechanism is reproduced from Payne et al. [56]. Pitch angle changes of $\pm 7.5^\circ$ centered around the design pitch angle can be realized. The spinner of the turbine houses the encapsulated strain gauge amplifiers for minimizing the transmission length of the unconditioned BRBM signals. The nacelle is fully waterproofed using o-rings. Redundancies are implemented where possible. Suitably rated cable glands are incorporated in the design for feeding the data and motor cables through the waterproof enclosure and into the tower. A three-component strain gauge is used to measure the aerodynamic turbine thrust. The steady rotor torque is estimated using the electrical moment provided by the drive inverter. Where possible, the nacelle is streamlined with parts made from filament-based additive manufacturing. The transition of the smaller outer nacelle diameter ($D_{N,1} = 0.13\text{ m}$) towards the larger part ($D_{N,2} = 0.155\text{ m}$) is realized with the computerized numerical control (CNC) milled centerpiece of the turbine (Table 2.1). Several safety sensors are included in the UBeRT test rig. Water ingress is detected at every o-ring location, utilizing self-made copper wire-based sensors. Their contacts are monitored by water switches, which send immediate signals to the superior acquisition system and a horn. If water enters the nacelle, it is most likely to creep in rather than flood the turbine rapidly. Hence, some time remains after detecting the water ingress to evacuate the turbine. This is done by tilting the tower to its upper resting position. Slippage of the coupling or the turbine shaft is identified by comparing a once-per-revolution signal with the signal of the motor encoder. The combination of the signals is also used to generate a ramp signal for triggering the PIV system, depending on the blade position. The nacelle accelerations in three directions are tracked with an accelerometer. The BRBMs are measured and monitored. Details on the dimensioning of all critical turbine components and additional insights into the design are extensively described in MT1 [1].

2.2 Test rig description

The turbine is attached to the measurement platform of the tow carriage by a $L_T = 4.961\text{ m}$ long tower (Figure 2.7). The tower is segmented into several pieces of four different cross-sections: a small tube with an outer diameter of $D_{T,1} = 0.112\text{ m}$ and an inner diameter of $d_{T,1} = 0.09\text{ m}$; a large tube with $D_{T,2} = 0.2\text{ m}$ and $d_{T,2} = 0.18\text{ m}$; and two solid sections with $D_{T,3} = 0.12\text{ m}$ and $D_{T,4} = 0.135\text{ m}$, where the bearings are located. Most of the tower sections are made from the tube with the large cross-section. A

Figure 2.7: The UBeRT test rig. (8) Fixed bearing. (9) Rail carriage and rails for axial traversability. (10) Floating bearing. (11) Tower segment with tilting hinge (not visible) for quick blade pitch changes and evacuation in case of water ingress. (12) Tower segment of 830 mm length with reduced outer diameter. (13) Free water surface.

fixed-floating pair of self-aligning roller bearings with a distance of 1.559 m is chosen for mounting the tower to the frame. The pairing counteracts the turbine thrust and all side forces due to misalignment. The tower is axially traversable relative to the underwater PIV system. Wake locations up to $5D$ downstream of the rotor plane can be investigated with the current setup. The tower design allows for the analysis of yawed turbine configurations. A tilting hinge is included in the design to enable quick access to the turbine, i.e., for pitch angle changes and the evacuation of the turbine. The pivot point is located 780 mm above the water's surface. The lower end of the tower becomes more slender for 830 mm. The reduced cross-section shall decrease the tower's drag regarding the passing tip vortices and thereby limit the artificial excitation of short-wave instabilities of the tip vortex helix (Figure 1.4b). A stiffening rod additionally supports the tower. Its connection point is submerged 1 m below the water level. The rotor-to-tower distance is 340 mm $\approx 0.5R$. Up- and downwind turbine setups can be investigated. Different fairing strategies for reducing the tower's drag can be implemented. From analytical considerations found in MT1 [1], the turbine deflection imposed by the design thrust $\mathcal{T}_{\text{des}} = 2220 \text{ N}$ is calculated to be 7.8 mm without a stiffening rod for support. The resulting rotor plane rotation is 0.18° . The simple analytical model will be extended in the present thesis by high-fidelity simulations. Additionally, an analysis of the dynamic properties of the UBeRT will be carried out and presented in Section 5.1.

Figure 2.8: Large towing tank and carriage at the Technische Universität Berlin from [57].

3 Methodology

The following paragraphs introduce the main methods used for modeling the aerodynamic and structural properties of the UBeRT test rig. Section 3.1 summarizes the main modeling principles of the BEM theory. Section 3.2 presents key aspects of the LLFVW method. In Section 3.3, the methods for representing the structural properties of the test rig numerically are established. Finally, the implementation of the strategies inside the QBLADE software environment is explained in Section 3.4.

3.1 Blade Element Momentum Theory

The BEM method is the most common modeling approach to assess the static loading on HAWTs [58, 59]. It combines the actuator disc theory with a discretized representation of the rotor blades. As introduced by Glauert [55], it assumes that the force on the blade element is the sole cause of changes in the axial momentum of the fluid passing the swept annulus of width dr [5, 60] (Figure 3.1). The flow around the elements is bound by their borders, i.e., spanwise interactions between the blade segments are inhibited. Additionally, the flow is assumed to be locally two-dimensional around each element. Thus, using the airfoil-specific polar data for deriving the loads on the element is enabled. Additionally, the global rotor characteristics, that is, thrust \mathcal{T} and thrust coefficient $C_{\mathcal{T}}$, torque \mathcal{Q} and torque coefficient $C_{\mathcal{Q}}$, and power \mathcal{P} and power coefficient $C_{\mathcal{P}}$ can be derived from the summation of all element-specific contributions ($d\mathcal{T}$, $d\mathcal{Q}$, ...). In its simplest form, the BEM theory describes the elementary forces imposed on the fluid flow as independent of the azimuthal position, i.e., the force is constant in the entire annulus [60, 61]. Figure 3.1 visualizes the fundamental kinematics of the BEM method. The undisturbed fluid flow of velocity \bar{U}_{∞} is decelerated to the rotor plane velocity \bar{U} . The magnitude of the reduction is quantified using the axial induction factor a (Equation 3.1a). The aerodynamic interaction of the blades with the fluid induces tangential loads in the rotor plane, which cause the turbine's torque \mathcal{Q} . The same force distribution, yet of opposing sign, is imposed on the fluid, causing the wake to rotate. The resulting increase in the tangential velocity seen by the blade is quantified by the tangential induction factor a^* (Equation (3.1b)) [59, 61, 62].

$$\bar{U} = (1 - a)\bar{U}_{\infty} \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\bar{U}_{\vartheta} = (1 + a^*)\Omega r \quad (3.1b)$$

The set of equations constituting the BEM theory is listed below.

The linear transformation between the airfoil coordinate system ($\mathbf{e}_{\eta}, \mathbf{e}_{\zeta}$) and the rotor plane coordinate system ($\mathbf{e}_N, \mathbf{e}_T$) is found (Equations (3.2)).

$$dF_N = dF_L \cos \varphi(r) + dF_D \sin \varphi(r) \quad C_N = C_L \cos \varphi(r) + C_D \sin \varphi(r) \quad (3.2a)$$

$$dF_T = dF_L \sin \varphi(r) - dF_D \cos \varphi(r) \quad C_T = C_L \sin \varphi(r) - C_D \cos \varphi(r) \quad (3.2b)$$

Where dF_N , dF_T , dF_L , and dF_D are the element-wise normal, tangential, lift, and drag forces. C_N , C_T , C_L , and C_D are the corresponding coefficients, defined in Equation (3.3).

$$C_i := \frac{2dF_i}{\rho \bar{U}_{\infty}^2 c(r) dr} \quad i, \in \{N, T, L, D\} \quad (3.3)$$

Both coordinate systems rotate with the angular velocity Ω around the rotor axis \mathbf{e}_x^{∞} . Equations (3.4a) and (3.4b) relate the inflow angle φ and the AoA α to the inflow conditions and the pitch angle β [59].

Figure 3.1: Kinematic inflow conditions and aerodynamic forces on a two-dimensional profile reproduced from [9], extended based on [61]. With the undisturbed inflow velocity \bar{U}_∞ , the inflow velocity at the rotor plane \bar{U} , the velocity Ωr due to the rotation of the blade with angular velocity Ω at radius location r and the resulting absolute mean velocity $\bar{q}(r)$. Blade chord $c(r)$, blade pitch angle $\beta(r)$, and angle of attack $\alpha(r)$. Infinitesimal lift dF_L and drag force dF_D . Resulting total force dF_{res} . Decomposed normal dF_n , i.e., thrust $d\mathcal{T}$, and tangential force dF_t . Rotor torque \mathcal{Q} .

$$\tan \varphi(r) = \frac{(1-a)\bar{U}_\infty}{(1+a^*)\Omega r} \quad (3.4a)$$

$$\alpha(r) = \varphi(r) - \beta(r) \quad (3.4b)$$

The blade solidity σ quantifies the ratio of the N_b blade surfaces $N_b c(r) dr$ to the area of the annulus $2\pi r dr$ (Equation (3.5)). The solidity affects the performance of a turbine by altering the shape of the $C_P - \lambda$ -curve. With decreasing solidity, the performance peak is flattened, i.e., the performance characteristics becomes less sensitive to changing λ values. However, larger maximum C_P values are achieved for an increasing number of blades, i.e., larger solidity [5].

$$\sigma(r) := \frac{c(r)N_b}{2\pi r} \quad (3.5)$$

Each individual segment of width dr contributes to the integral rotor loads by Equations (3.6) [61].

$$d\mathcal{T}(r) = N_b \frac{\rho \bar{U}_\infty^2 (1-a)^2}{2 \sin^2 \varphi(r)} c(r) C_N dr \quad (3.6a)$$

$$d\mathcal{Q}(r) = N_b \frac{\rho \bar{U}_\infty (1-a) \Omega r (1+a^*)}{2 \sin \varphi(r) \cos \varphi(r)} c(r) C_T r dr \quad (3.6b)$$

$$d\mathcal{P}(r) = \Omega d\mathcal{Q}(r) \quad (3.6c)$$

For the induction factors, two compact expressions can be found (Equations (3.7)) [6].

$$a = \frac{1}{\frac{4 \sin^2(\varphi)}{\sigma C_N} + 1} \quad (3.7a)$$

$$a^* = \frac{1}{\frac{4 \sin(\varphi) \cos(\varphi)}{\sigma C_T} - 1} \quad (3.7b)$$

The above listed set of equations fully constitute the static HAWT loads within the assumptions of the simplest BEM model. However, no closed solution to the system of equations is found. An iterative solution strategy must be employed for calculating the induction factors and segment-wise loads. Several algorithms to the iteration can be found in the literature. Typically, the following approach is implemented [61]:

Two corrective semi-empirical measures are typically included in BEM tools to improve the accuracy of the results. PRANDTL's tip loss factor corrects the assumption of an infinite number of blades. It causes the induction factors to become functions of the radius r (Equations (3.8)), where $\mu := r/R$. The correction is derived from modeling individual vortex sheets in the wake, induced by radial circulation changes along individual blades [5].

$$\xi_P(\mu, \lambda) = \frac{2}{\pi} \arccos \left(e^{-\frac{N_b}{2} \frac{1-\mu}{\mu \sin \varphi(r)}} \right) \quad (3.8)$$

The introduction of the tip loss factor extends the constituting system of the BEM method to Equations (3.9) for the induction factors.

$$a = \frac{1}{\frac{4\xi_P \sin^2(\varphi)}{\sigma C_N} + 1} \quad (3.9a)$$

$$a^* = \frac{1}{\frac{4\xi_P \sin(\varphi) \cos(\varphi)}{\sigma C_T} - 1} \quad (3.9b)$$

According to Hansen [61], Equations (3.9) should be used for calculating the induction factors rather than applying Equations (3.7).

GLAUERT's correction includes an empirical extension of the calculation of the thrust coefficient C_T for axial induction factors a exceeding a certain threshold. The correction is necessary since the simple momentum theory breaks down for $a > 0.4$. Several empirical relations between the thrust coefficient and the axial induction factor can be found from fits with experimental data (e.g., Equation (3.10)) [61].

$$C_T = \begin{cases} 4a(1-a)\xi_P & a \leq \frac{1}{3} \\ 4a(1 - \frac{5-3a}{4}a)\xi_P & a > \frac{1}{3} \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

Madsen et al. [63] summarize and compare results from the classical BEM and the actuator disc theory. Several extensions for including wake effects are presented. A stationary polar grid is introduced, discretizing the rotor disc radially and azimuthally to account for inhomogeneous inflow conditions and loading. The local induction factors are estimated from the induced velocities of the two neighboring blades and weighted by their azimuthal distance [62].

For calculating the average loading and the annual energy production of a rotor configuration, steady BEM strategies are sufficient [61]. However, when transient processes are to be simulated, e.g., extreme load conditions from gusts or inflow direction changes [64, 65], an unsteady BEM (uBEM) implementation can be used. Typically, uBEM methods are combined with a structural model of the blades, the nacelle, and the tower to account for structural vibrations and thereby induced velocities [61]. Different models are available in the literature for including dynamic effects in the calculation of the blade loads and the structural response of the turbine. Henriksen et al. [66] introduce a full-state dynamic inflow aerodynamic model that captures wake and load interactions. The model projects how changes in the tangential and normal induction factors affect the temporal development of the local velocity components. The time constants of the dynamic inflow are derived from the rotor scale and the undisturbed fluid velocity \bar{U}_∞ . Alternatively, a simplified version of the full-state dynamic inflow model is introduced. It assumes a steady tangential velocity equal to the predictions of the classical BEM theory and omits the radial dependency of the normal velocity. The simplification is justified by its straightforward applicability to model-based control and state estimation algorithms. Silva et al. [67] describe a possible adapted implementation of the uBEM method, where a temporal iteration is wrapped around the classical BEM algorithm. Hansen [61] gives further insight into the typical implementation of uBEM methods.

3.2 Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake Method

The LLFVW method models inviscid potential flows by utilizing a vortex-based representation of the flow field. The increased modeling depth reduces the number of necessary semi-empirical correction methods. Tip and root losses, response delays of the wake to transient conditions, and the radial induction are inherent to the LLFVW implementation [68]. The increased accuracy compared to BEM methods is offset by growing computational costs [58, 59]. Van Garrel [69] extensively describes a robust and accessible implementation of the LLFVW method. The "lifting" character of, e.g., an

Figure 3.2: a) Nomenclature used in the BIOT-SAVART law Equation (3.11). b) Nomenclature of horseshoe vortex induced velocity, reproduced from Phillips et al. [70].

airfoil is lumped into a single vortex, placed at the quarter-chord location. The expansion of the airfoil towards the blade results in the definition of a line vortex, i.e., a lifting line. The model is limited to planar or slightly curved blade geometries without strong radial flow interactions. No thickness or displacement effects are included in the model. In accordance with KELVIN's vortex theorem, all included vortex lines are closed vortex rings. More specifically, the implemented vortex system consists of horseshoe vortices, where the bound portion is placed coincident with the quarter-chord line. The trailing vortices are aligned with the local direction of the chord and are placed on every node of the spatial discretization. Thus, except at the blade tip and root, the neighboring trailing segments of adjacent horseshoe vortices share the same position [70]. The induced solenoidal velocity field $\vec{U}^{\text{ind}}(\vec{x})$ of a vortex filament¹ with constant vortex strength Γ can be evaluated applying BIOT-SAVART's law (Equation (3.11)). It is derived from the potential theory, as the flow outside the filament boundary is irrotational [69, 71, 72].

$$\vec{U}^{\text{ind}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \oint_{\mathcal{C}} \frac{\vec{f} \times d\vec{l}}{|\vec{f}(\vec{l})|^3} \quad (3.11)$$

$\vec{f} = \vec{x} - \vec{f}_O$ is the vector pointing from the vortex filament, located at \vec{f}_O , to the point of interest, located at \vec{x} (Figure 3.2a). $|\cdot|$ describes the absolute of the vector. The integral must be calculated along the filament curve \mathcal{C} . A horseshoe vortex consists of three straight vortex filaments (Figure 3.2b). The induced velocity field of one straight filament of finite length can be derived from Equation (3.11) and is commonly stated as in Equation (3.12a) [73]. However, the induced velocity becomes indetermined not only at the filament location (e.g., $\vec{f}_1 = \vec{0}$), but wherever \vec{f}_1 is collinear to \vec{f}_2 . Therefore, following Phillips et al. [70], the expression can be reduced to Equation (3.12b). Now, the denominator of Equation (3.12b) behaves only singularly when the evaluation point approaches the vortex line itself.

¹Vortex filaments are vortex tubes of infinitely small cross-sectional area.

$$\vec{U}^{\text{ind}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \vec{f}_O \cdot \left(\frac{\vec{f}_1}{|\vec{f}_1|} - \frac{\vec{f}_2}{|\vec{f}_2|} \right) \frac{\vec{f}_1 \times \vec{f}_2}{|\vec{f}_1 \times \vec{f}_2|^2} \quad (3.12a)$$

$$\vec{U}^{\text{ind}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \frac{|\vec{f}_1| + |\vec{f}_2|}{|\vec{f}_1||\vec{f}_2|(|\vec{f}_1||\vec{f}_2| + \vec{f}_1 \cdot \vec{f}_2)} (\vec{f}_1 \times \vec{f}_2) \quad (3.12b)$$

This singular behavior is typically circumvented by adding the cut-off radius δ^2 to the denominator of Equation (3.12b) [69]. For evaluation points closer to the filament than δ , typically a linear function for the azimuthal velocity is implemented, i.e., within the vortex core, a rigid-body rotation of the fluid is assumed (RANKINE vortex [74]). LAMB-OSEEN [75] and BATCHELOR [42, 46] vortices are examples of more elaborate vortex models. Figure 3.3 shows the schematics of a BATCHELOR vortex. It prescribes a GAUSSIAN vorticity, inducing azimuthal $U_\Theta(\rho)$ and axial $U_\Xi(\rho)$ velocities in the natural vortex coordinate system $(\mathbf{e}_\Xi, \mathbf{e}_\Theta, \mathbf{e}_\rho)$ following Equations (3.13). The reduced radius parameter ρ_{red} can be fitted from experimental data based on the location of the maximum swirl velocity U_Θ by $\rho_{\text{red}} \approx 0.8929\rho_{\text{max}}$. The maximum defines the core size of the vortex [43].

$$U_\Theta(\rho) = \frac{\Gamma}{2\pi\rho} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\rho^2}{\rho_{\text{red}}^2}} \right) \quad (3.13a)$$

$$U_\Xi(\rho) = \max U_\Xi e^{-\frac{\rho^2}{\rho_{\text{red}}^2}} \quad (3.13b)$$

As can be seen from the profiles visualized in Figure 3.3, the swirl velocity follows a point-symmetric linear trend within the vortex core and reaches its maximum at the boundary of the core. For larger ρ , the swirl velocity converges asymptotically towards zero. The axial velocity profile is axisymmetric with a maximum at the center axis of the vortex core. Beyond the boundary of the core, the axial velocity component converges to zero.

The application of BIOT-SAVART's law (Equation (3.12b)) to a complete horseshoe vortex composed of a bound and two trailing vortex segments yields Equation (3.14) [70].

$$\vec{U}^{\text{ind}}(\vec{x}) = \frac{\Gamma}{4\pi} \left(\frac{\vec{U}_\infty \times \vec{f}_2}{|\vec{f}_2|(|\vec{f}_2| - \vec{U}_\infty \cdot \vec{f}_2)} + \frac{(|\vec{f}_1| + |\vec{f}_2|)(\vec{f}_1 \times \vec{f}_2)}{|\vec{f}_1||\vec{f}_2|(|\vec{f}_2||\vec{f}_1| + \vec{f}_1 \cdot \vec{f}_2)} - \frac{\vec{U}_\infty \times \vec{f}_1}{|\vec{f}_1|(|\vec{f}_1| - \vec{U}_\infty \cdot \vec{f}_1)} \right) \quad (3.14)$$

The LLFVW theory evaluates the velocities and generated lift forces at points along the quarter-chord line ($\vec{x} \in \vec{\eta}_{25}$). The influence of all lifting line segments must be considered. Equation (3.15) describes the summation over all N horseshoe vortex elements, where Equation (3.14) is utilized for deriving the individual velocity components. Only one evaluation point per horseshoe vortex j is chosen for representing the velocity distribution along the element. In Equation (3.14), the center term refers to the induced velocity of the bound portion of the horseshoe vortex. For $i = j$ in Equations (3.15), the term is omitted since a straight vortex segment does not induce any velocity along its axis. Details on the implementation can be found in Phillips et al. [70] for aircraft applications, van Garrel [69] for a wind turbine-specific implementation, and Katz et al. [73] for general insights in vortex lattice

Figure 3.3: Schematics of the azimuthal and axial velocity profiles of a BATCHELOR vortex. Reproduced from Quaranta et al. [43].

methods.

$$\vec{U}_i(\vec{x}_i) = \vec{U}_\infty + \vec{U}_{\text{bl}} + \sum_j^N \vec{U}_j^{\text{ind}} \quad (3.15)$$

\vec{U}_{bl} is the blade motion-related fluid velocity, calculated from Equation (3.16). The blade motion can either be caused by the aeroelastic response of a structural model, the rigid body motion of the blade, or both.

$$\vec{U}_{\text{bl}} = -\frac{\vec{x}_i(t_k) - \vec{x}_i(t_{k-1})}{\tau} \quad (3.16)$$

t_{k-1} and t_k are consecutive time instances of temporal distance τ . After evaluating the onset velocity $\vec{U}_i(\vec{x}_i)$, a local AoA α_i can be calculated and correlated to a lift and drag coefficient. Equations (3.3) enable the calculation of the related forces, where $i \in \{L, D\}$ and $\overline{U}_\infty^2 \mapsto |\vec{U}|^2$. Additionally, KUTTA-JOUKOWSKY'S theorem relates the force vector of a lifting line segment $d\vec{l}$ to the generated lift forces $d\vec{F}_L$ (Equation (3.17)) [69, 70].

$$d\vec{F}_L = \rho \Gamma \vec{U} \times d\vec{l} \quad (3.17)$$

In general, the LLFVW is iteratively solved. However, for cases of reduced complexity, such as thin airfoils, a closed solution exists. The iteration typically reads as follows [62, 69, 76]:

- | | |
|---|---|
| <p>a) Initialization
Initialize circulation on lifting line Γ_i.</p> <p>b) Onset velocities \vec{U}_i
Calculate onset velocities with Equation (3.15)</p> <p>c) AoAs α_i
Calculate AoAs from \vec{U}_i</p> <p>d) Polar lookup
Obtain $C_{L,i}(\alpha_i)$ and $C_{D,i}(\alpha_i)$ from the airfoil's polars</p> <p>e) Reevaluate Γ_i
Calculate new Γ_i distribution from equating Equations (3.17) and (3.3)</p> <p>f) Comparison
If new Γ_i deviate more than threshold, iterate</p> <p>g) Load calculation
Calculate segment-wise blade loads</p> | <p style="font-size: 2em;">}</p> <p style="font-size: 2em;">LLFVW</p> |
|---|---|

Once a convergence state is reached, the blade is advanced depending on the current rotational speed and the temporal discretization τ . Additionally, all free vortex elements of strengths according to KUTTA'S condition (Equations (3.18)) are convected with the local inflow and induced velocities [76]. x points along the lifting line in spanwise direction.

$$\Gamma_{\text{trl}} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\text{bnd}}}{\partial x} dx \quad (3.18a)$$

$$\Gamma_{\text{shd}} = \frac{\partial \Gamma_{\text{bnd}}}{\partial t} dt \quad (3.18b)$$

Unlike the BEM method, several aerodynamic effects are inherently modeled in the LLFVW theory due to the increased model fidelity. Especially the influence of the wake on the characteristics of the rotor is directly represented. Nevertheless, LLFVW models are typically supplemented by stall delay [77], dynamic stall [78], and tower shadow models for increasing the simulation accuracy [68]. Perez-Becker et al. [68] extensively compare the performance differences between the (unsteady) BEM and LLFVW implementations regarding their suitability for design load case simulations of the Danish Technical University 10 MW Reference Wind Turbine. For stationary baseline scenarios, both methods predict similar performance characteristics for all relevant wind speeds. For turbulent load case simulations, however, the uBEM implementation commands a higher activity of the controllers, causing considerably larger fatigue and extreme loads compared with the LLFVW simulations.

3.3 Structural Beam Formulation

For accurately modeling the performance of a turbine throughout its parameter regime, a structural model for the blades, the nacelle, and the tower is needed since their structural response influences the turbine's performance characteristics. Typically, multi-body finite element analysis (FEA) formulations in the time domain are implemented, where individual components can be modeled as rigid or represented by suitable structure elements [79]. The translational and rotational motions of rigidly modeled bodies are derived from the motion of their centers of gravity (COGs). The elasticity of the turbine is captured by constituting each component from N_{elem} rigid sub-elements. The deformation state of the component is then derived by superimposing the load-driven deformation of the individual elements [59]. EULER-BERNOULLI beam elements are usually selected for structural wind turbine simulations as they represent an accurate model for slender bodies. Longitudinal, torsional, and bending deflections, including loads while neglecting shear, are accounted for. The cross-sectional properties of the beam are derived from the input geometry, including material-dependent characteristics. The turbine bodies can either be linked by force elements, e.g., springs or dampers, or kinematically, or by combining both [79]. For large deflections and where the system's nonlinearities must be accounted for, co-rotational [80] or floating-frame-of-reference [81] formulations were proven suitable [58, 59, 79]. Figure 3.4 visualizes the reduction of a multidimensional geometry to an interlinked multi-body formulation. The tower and the blades (Figure 3.4a, markers (1) and (2)) of the turbine are modeled as elastic components composed of EULER-BERNOULLI beam elements (Figure 3.4b, markers (7) and (8)). The nacelle is assumed to be rigid and represented by its center of gravity (COG) (Figure 3.4a, marker (3)). Nacelle and tower and blades and nacelle are connected by revolute constraints (Figure 3.4b, markers (5) and (6)), allowing their relative rotation based on actuator signals. The multi-body representation of the turbine based on beam elements reduces the necessary degrees of freedom (DOFs) to increase the computational efficacy. Additional details on common approaches for modeling the aeroelastic response of wind turbines can be found in [58, 79, 82] for QBLADE, in [83–85] for OPENFAST, and in [86] for HAWC2.

Figure 3.4: Structural representation of a turbine by beam elements inside QBLADE: **a)** Full turbine beam model. (1) Substructure body. (2) Blade body. (3) Rigid nacelle with center of gravity highlighted. (4) Constraint nodes. Bearing locations. **b)** Detail view of turbine beam model. (5) Nacelle-substructure connection. Revolute constraint. (6) Blade-nacelle connection. Revolute constraint. (7) Structural node. (8) Beam element with cross-sectional properties.

3.4 The Software QBlade

In this thesis, the aeroelastic simulation tool QBLADE is utilized for simulating the UBERT. QBLADE offers implementations of the uBEM and LLFVW theories for modeling the turbine’s aerodynamic performance and wake characteristics. The open-source multi-physics library PROJECT CHRONO [82] is incorporated into QBLADE to model the aerodynamic and structural interactions imposed by the incoming wind field. In QBLADE, the turbine is typically created starting with its aerodynamic performance. XFOIL [53] can be used to generate sets of two-dimensional polars for each airfoil constituting the wind turbine blade. Thereafter, the polars must be extrapolated for AoA values of $\pm 180^\circ$ based on MONTGOMERIE’s [87] or VITERNA’s [88] approach. Manual adjustments of the parameters can be made [58]. Alternatively, (experimentally) acquired polars can be fed into the software. QBLADE includes a blade design module where the blade discretization scheme, the section chord, the blade pitch, the location of the pitch axis, and additional blade properties can be assigned. For the blade design, a static BEM simulation can be started to acquire averaged rotor characteristics. For full turbine simulations, including the use of the LLFVW theory, a structural model for the tower and the blades, and the position of the COG and the mass of the nacelle are required. The most recent QBLADE release (v.2.0.4.9) has been developed as part of the Horizon 2020 project FLOATECH [89]. It enables the representation of more complicated sub-structures, i.e., floating turbine foundations,

and more elaborate boundary constraints. The turbine definition is done using the graphical user interface (GUI) of QBLADE's TURBINE DEFINITION module. The structural properties of the individual components must be provided by the user in tabulated form. Once the turbine is fully implemented, a simulation definition is created. Temporal and spatial discretization schemes, the incoming (transient) wind and/or wave field, an assigned turbine behavior including boundary constraints, and a set of environmental properties must be assigned. Data-saving can be switched on and off, depending on the necessary post-processing. The enterprise license of QBLADE additionally allows an automatic modal analysis of the linearized multi-body system at the end of the simulation, once the rotor reaches its initial azimuthal location. In QBLADE, the co-simulation is coupled loosely, where the structural iteration proceeds with a smaller time step ($\tau_{\text{struct}} = 1/k \tau_{\text{aero}}$, $k = \{1, \dots, K\}$, $K \in \mathcal{N}$, K is user input) compared to the iteration of the aerodynamic calculation [79]. In the LLFVW implementation, the wake is convected and augmented by the shed elements once the structural time step reaches the next global time step [59, 90].

All the necessary information on how to use QBLADE is available in the online documentation [58]. Insights into the modeling approaches implemented in QBLADE can be found in Marten [79] and Marten et al. [76]. QBLADE is thoroughly validated by code-to-code comparisons [59, 62, 68, 78, 90, 91] and against available experimental data [76].

4 Structural Model

The following chapter defines the structural model of the turbine (Section 4.1) and the tower (Section 4.2). The constraints of the model are summarized in Section 4.3. Measures for validating the numerical model are defined and analyzed in Section 4.4. The generated input files for QBLADE of the final UBeRT model can be found in Appendix B. The input files for the validation are listed in Appendix A.

4.1 Turbine Model

Three types of input files are used to pass the structural properties of the turbine and the tower to QBLADE. The first summarizes the cross-sectional properties of the $N_b = 3$ blades. The $R = 650$ mm rotor of the UBeRT is based on the SG6040 airfoil found in Lyon et al. [52] (Figure 4.1). Interpolated geometries made from 33% and 66% circular profiles are incorporated for the first 11% of the blade (Figure 2.3). The hub diameter of the turbine is $R_{\text{hub}} = 65$ mm $= 0.1R$. Table 4.1 summarizes the radial starting locations of the airfoils and the chordwise location of the pitch axis. The chord and blade pitch as functions of r are plotted in Figure 2.2a (solid line). The blade is aerodynamically discretized into $N_{\text{aero,elem}} = 30$ for the uBEM and $N_{\text{aero,elem}} = 20$ for the LLFVW simulations based on a cosine node placement. $N_{\text{struct,elem}} = 20$ linearly distributed structural nodes (*DISC*)¹ are used to resolve the elasticity of the blades.

The blades are CNC-milled from solid 1.4301 stainless-steel ($E = 2 \times 10^{11}$ N m⁻², $\rho = 7900$ kg m⁻³, $G = 79 \times 10^9$ N m⁻²). The total blade mass yields $m_{\text{bl}} = 4.829$ kg. To pass the blade models to QBLADE's TURBINE DEFINITION module providing a set of tabulated structural properties is required (e.g., Appendix B.2 for the blade input file). A turbine beam model is necessary to capture the aeroelastic response and interaction of the entire turbine model. For deriving the area-dependent properties of the blade sections at radial positions r_j , the contours are approximated as polygons with N vertices at the coordinates (x_i, y_i) . The coordinate system $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y\}$ of every cross-section is located at $(0.5, 0)$ in $\{\mathbf{e}_\eta, \mathbf{e}_\zeta\}$ and aligned with the chord [58]. Figure 4.2 visualizes the location of the reference coordinate system [58, 61]. At every position r_j , the reference system is rotated according to the local blade pitch $\beta_j(r_j)$. Hence, in $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y\}$, the SG6040 airfoil appears only scaled by the local blade chord $c_j(r_j)$. The area and the location of the centroid for the given foil coordinates in $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y\}$

Figure 4.1: Airfoils of the UBeRT blades: *SG6040* (base profile), *-33circ* (33% circular, 66% SG6040), *-66circ* (66% circular, 33% SG6040)

Table 4.1: UBeRT blades: Radial airfoil and chordwise pitch axis locations in the blade root coordinate system.

Radius [mm]	Relative Radius [%]	Pitch Axis [η]	Airfoil
0	0	0.5	Circular
32	4.92	0.37	-66circ
112	17.23	0.3	-33circ
130	20	0.26	SG6040
140	21.54	0.25	SG6040

¹Italic terms refer to the nomenclature of QBLADE's structural input files (Appendix A and B)

are calculated by Equations (4.1) [92].

$$A_j = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (x_i - x_{i+1})(y_i + y_{i+1}) \quad (4.1a)$$

$$x_{m,j} = \frac{1}{6A_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (x_i + x_{i+1})(x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i) \quad (4.1b)$$

$$y_{m,j} = \frac{1}{6A_j} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (y_i + y_{i+1})(x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i) \quad (4.1c)$$

QBLADE requires the location of the centroid normalized by the local blade chord $c_j(r_j)$ (Equations 4.2) [58].

$$x_{mc,j} = \frac{x_{m,j}}{c_j(r_j)} \quad XCM \quad (4.2a)$$

$$y_{mc,j} = \frac{y_{m,j}}{c_j(r_j)} \quad YCM \quad (4.2b)$$

For a blade based on a single geometry, Equations (4.2) yield a constant normalized location of the centroid. The center of elasticity of the blade is assumed to coincide with the centroid position (XCE : $x_{ec,j} = x_{mc,j}$, YCE : $y_{ec,j} = y_{mc,j}$). The EULER-BERNOULLI beam model omits shear (GA , KSX , KSY set to zero). Hence, the location ($x_{sc,j}, y_{sc,j}$) has no influence on the structural dynamics of the model (XCS , YCS : $x_{sc,j} = y_{sc,j} = 0$). The second moments of area are calculated in $R : \{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y\}$ according to Equations 4.3a until 4.3d. The angle χ between the principle bending axis ($\mathbf{e}_u, \mathbf{e}_v$) and the reference coordinate system $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y\}$ is derived from Equation 4.3e [92] (Figure 4.2). For the UBERT blades, χ is constant for every relative radial positions greater than 11 % (20 % in the blade root coordinate system) as only one airfoil is used.

$$I_{xx,j}^R = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (y_i^2 + y_i y_{i+1} + y_{i+1}^2)(x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i) \quad (4.3a)$$

$$I_{yy,j}^R = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (x_i^2 + x_i x_{i+1} + x_{i+1}^2)(x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i) \quad (4.3b)$$

$$I_{xy,j}^R = -\frac{1}{24} \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} (x_i y_{i+1} + 2x_i y_i + 2x_{i+1} y_{i+1} + x_{i+1} y_i)(x_i y_{i+1} - x_{i+1} y_i) \quad (4.3c)$$

$$I_{p,j}^R = I_{xx,j}^R + I_{yy,j}^R \quad (4.3d)$$

$$\chi_j = \frac{1}{2} \arctan \frac{2I_{xy,j}^R}{I_{xx,j}^R - I_{yy,j}^R} \quad STRPIT \quad (4.3e)$$

The parallel axis theorem allows shifting an area property to any other location. The projection of the second moments of area to the centroid is yielded by Equations (4.4) [92].

$$I_{xx,j} = I_{xx,j}^R - y_{m,j}^2 A_j \quad (4.4a)$$

$$I_{yy,j} = I_{yy,j}^R - x_{m,j}^2 A_j \quad (4.4b)$$

$$I_{xy,j} = I_{xy,j}^R + x_{m,j} y_{m,j} A_j \quad (4.4c)$$

$$I_{p,j} = I_{xx,j} + I_{yy,j} \quad (4.4d)$$

Figure 4.2: Coordinate system used for the definition of the cross-sectional parameters of the structural blade model. Angle χ between the principle bending axis $\{\mathbf{e}_u, \mathbf{e}_v\}$ and the reference coordinate system $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y\}$. $\beta_j(r_j)$ blade pitch angle and $c_j(r_j)$ chord at radial location r_j . $\beta|_{tip}$ blade pitch angle and $c|_{tip}$ chord at the tip. Reproduced from QBLADE's user guide [58] and [61].

The radii of gyration follow from Equations (4.5) [93].

$$i_{x,j} = \sqrt{\frac{I_{xx,j}}{A_j}} \quad (4.5a)$$

$$i_{y,j} = \sqrt{\frac{I_{yy,j}}{A_j}} \quad (4.5b)$$

Normalization utilizing the local blade chord yields Equations (4.6).

$$i_{xc,j} = \frac{i_{x,j}}{c_j(r_j)} \quad RGX \quad (4.6a)$$

$$i_{yc,j} = \frac{i_{y,j}}{c_j(r_j)} \quad RGY \quad (4.6b)$$

The structural model of the blades is complemented by stiffness and mass parameters, depending on a relative radial location $r_{R,j}$ (Equations (4.7)).

$$L_{bl} = R - R_{hub} \quad (4.7a)$$

$$r_{R,j} = \frac{r_j - R_{hub}}{L_{bl}} \quad LENFRACT \quad (4.7b)$$

$$m_{R,j} = \rho A_j \quad MASSD \quad (4.7c)$$

$EI_{xx,j}$ (EIx), $EI_{yy,j}$ (EIy), $GI_{p,j}$ (GJ), and EA_j (EA) are calculated based on Equations (4.4a), (4.4b), (4.4d), and (4.1a).

Following Deichmann [93], the RAYLEIGH damping coefficient ($RAYLEIGHDMP$) is left at QBLADE's default value of 0.0024, as the damping of the blades is not analyzed. Scaling of the structural cross-sectional properties is disabled ($STIFFTUNER$, $MASSTUNER$ set to zero). All three blades are assumed to be structurally identical in the simulation. The input file for the structural simulation of the blades is provided in Appendix B.2.

Overall turbine dimensions and global nacelle, drivetrain, and brake parameters are defined in the main definition file (Appendix B.1). Table 4.2 summarizes the chosen parameters, derived from the SOLIDWORKS model. The precone and the shaft tilt angle are set to 0° ($PRECONE$, $SHFTTILT$). Figure 4.3 visualizes the relative distances of the coordinate systems at the tower bottom (TB) and the rotor plane (RP). The \mathbf{e}_x -direction of the tower bottom system is aligned with the inflow direction. \mathbf{e}_z constitutes the tower axis. The \mathbf{e}_x axis, located at the rotor plane, coincides with the rotational axis of the main shaft. \mathbf{e}_z is normal to the still water level. Both \mathbf{e}_y directions are chosen to yield a regular Cartesian coordinate system. The distance of the rotor plane to the tower axis is 400 mm

(*OVERHANG*) and the distance from the tower bottom to the shaft axis is 166 mm (*TWR2SHFT*). Contrarily to conventional ground-fixed HAWTs, the UBeRT hangs from the measurement platform of the towing carriage (Figure 2.7). Hence, the gravitational acceleration points relatively in the opposite direction. The locations of QBLADE’s coordinate systems have to be considered to represent the conditions of the UBeRT test rig. For example, the rotational axis is below the tower bottom node, which has to be accounted for by providing a negative distance. Another particularity of the simulation of the UBeRT turbine inside QBLADE is that the entire tower is defined as a substructure object. This allows the inclusion of hydrodynamic forces on the submerged part of the turbine. Hence, the tower height property (*TWRHEIGHT*) is set to zero (Table 4.2). The nacelle mass and COG are provided, excluding all rotating parts (hub, blades). The mass properties of the blades are inherently modeled by providing their cross-sectional properties. The hub mass and rotational inertia comprise all rotating parts except the blades. Drivetrain-specific parameters, such as the gearbox ratio, are provided. However, no RPM controller is implemented in the model. For the test cases where acceleration ramps are prescribed to the rotor, no dynamic behavior of the drive train is modeled. The main definition file (Appendix B.1) also includes the relative paths to the blade and the substructure files. Sensors can be placed at any relative location. No pitch or yaw errors are assigned to the controllers.

Figure 4.3: Relative nacelle dimensions: Overhang and tower-to-shaft distance.

Table 4.2: Structural Underwater Berlin Research Turbine model: Turbine setup and mass properties.

Description	QBlade Naming	Value	Unit
<i>Geometry</i>			
Blade precone angle	<i>PRECONE</i>	0	°
Main shaft tilt angle	<i>SHFTTILT</i>	0	°
Distance rotor plane to tower axis	<i>OVERHANG</i>	0.400	m
Distance tower top node to shaft axis	<i>TWR2SHFT</i>	-0.166	m
<i>Nacelle w/o blades and hub</i>			
Nacelle mass	<i>NACMASS</i>	57.31	kg
Nacelle COG	<i>NACCMX, ...Y, ...Z</i>	(0.211,0,-0.147)	m
Nacelle yaw inertia around COG	<i>NACYNER</i>	5.21	kg m ²
Yaw bearing mass	<i>YAWBRMASS</i>	0	kg
<i>Drive train and brake</i>			
Hub mass	<i>HUBMASS</i>	13.04	kg
Hub rotational	<i>HUBINER</i>	0.0179	kg m ²
Gear box ratio	<i>GBRATIO</i>	12	
Gear box efficiency	<i>GBOXEFF</i>	95	%
Drive train model	<i>DRTRDOF</i>	false	true / false
Brake torque	<i>BRKTORQUE</i>	10	Nm
Tower height	<i>TWRHEIGHT</i>	0	m

4.2 Tower Model

The beam model of the tower is included in the QBLADE setup as a substructure object to increase the modeling freedom. In QBLADE, the mass density and kinematic viscosity of water and air are interchanged². Thereby, the entire turbine is treated as being fully submerged. However, if no hydrodynamic coefficients (*HYDROMEMBERCOEFF*) are provided for individual substructure members, the occurring forces will be zero. Alternatively, for the substructure part that is actually submerged, hydrodynamic forces could be considered. In the input file, Appendix B.3, the water depth is set to zero (*WATERDEPTH*). The fluid density (*WATERDENSITY*) is set to $\rho = 998.22 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$ (Table 2.1). The structure is affixed to the carriage (*ISFLOATING* false) and incorporated into the measurement domain such that it hangs one meter above the ground ($L_{\text{offset}} = 1 \text{ m}$). The substructure points towards larger ground distances (Figure 3.4a). Table 4.3 summarizes the length of the individual tower members. The ground offset is applied to the absolute location column. Since the turbine is directly connected to the substructure, the position of the transition piece is equal to the nacelle node (*TP_INTERFACE_POS*: (0,0,1)). No substructure mass matrix (*SUB_MASS*) is provided, as the turbine does not float. Six different sub-elements (*SUBELEMENTS*) are selected to represent the UBeRT. Four different cross-sections are relevant: two tubes and two solid sections. The cross-sectional properties could be derived from the equations listed in Section 4.1. However, for simple geometries, analytical expressions for the area integrals can be derived (Equations (4.8)). The profiles are axisymmetric which results in $x_{ec,j} = x_{mc,j} = x_{sc,j} = y_{ec,j} = y_{mc,j} = x_{sc,j} = 0$ (*XCM*, *YCM*, *XCE*, *YCE*, *XCS*, *YCS*). Shear is omitted for the tower (*GA*, *KSX*, *KSY* set to zero). The structural pitch angle χ_j (*STRPIT*) is zero for the entire tower as the reference coordinate system is aligned with the principle axis system.

$$A_j = \frac{\pi}{4}(D^2 - d^2) \quad (4.8a)$$

$$I_{xx,j} = I_{yy,j} = \frac{\pi}{64}(D^4 - d^4) \quad (4.8b)$$

$$I_{p,j} = I_{xx,j} + I_{yy,j} \quad (4.8c)$$

$$i_{xc,j} = i_{yc,j} = \sqrt{\frac{I_{xx,j}}{A_j} \frac{1}{D_j}} \quad RGX, RGY \quad (4.8d)$$

The tower is manufactured out of 1.4404 stainless-steel ($E = 2 \times 10^{11} \text{ N m}^{-2}$, $\rho = 8000 \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, $G = 79 \times 10^9 \text{ N m}^{-2}$). In QBLADE, the cross-sectional properties of the sub-elements must be provided in tabulated form (Appendix B.3). Joints can be defined at every Cartesian position (*SUBJOINTS*). Two

Table 4.3: Structural Underwater Berlin Research Turbine tower model: Members, bearings, and flanges.

Comp. Index	Type	Length [m]	Abs. Loc. [m]
Mem. 1	Small tube	0.829	1
Mem. 2	Large tube	0.505	1.829
Mem. 3	Large tube	1	2.334
Mem. 4	Large tube	0.78	3.334
Mem. 5	Large tube	0.188	4.114
Mem. 6	Solid	0.2	4.302
Mem. 7	Solid	0.2	4.402
Mem. 8	Large tube	1.331	4.502
Mem. 9	Solid	0.128	5.833
Bear. 1	Lower		4.402
Bear. 2	Upper		5.961
Stiff. rod			2.334
Mass [kg]			
Fl. 1	Round	2.93	1
Fl. 2	Round	9.93	1.829
Fl. 3	Square	9.97	4.114
Fl. 4	Round	18.8	4.302
Fl. 5	Round	18.8	4.502
Fl. 6	Round	10.37	5.833

²Compare MT1 [1] on how the steady BEM characteristics were derived.

joint positions are connected by a sub-element and constitute a sub-member (*SUBMEMBERS*) [58]. The UBeRT substructure is defined to consist of nine members, collected in Table 4.3. The first member is made of the $D = 112$ mm steel tube, which reaches beyond the blade tip. The $D = 200$ mm tower section, which connects the first tube and the hinge, is segmented into three members: one reaching from the flange to the location of the stiffening rod, a second one from there to the still water level, and a third member from the still water level to the hinge (Figure 2.7, Table 4.3). Member five connects the hinge flange with the bottom flange of the lower bearing section. The solid section of the lower bearing location is split into two members to assure the placement of a structural node at the location of the bearing. The large tube between the lower and the upper bearing is represented by member eight, and the solid upper bearing location is represented by member nine. The connection flanges are included as point masses at their respective nodal positions. Their mass is directly extracted from the fully resolved computer-aided design (CAD) assembly in SOLIDWORKS. Table 4.3 comprises the locations of the bearings and the anchor point of the stiffening rod. However, the simulations are carried out without the extra member to increase their comparability with the high-fidelity model inside SOLIDWORKS SIMULATION. For future work, the stiffening rod could be included in the QBLADE simulation as an individual member. Studies could be conducted on the influence of the mounting angle and the anchor location. In the sub-member table of the substructure definition file (Appendix B.3), a set of hydrodynamic coefficients (*HyCoID*) containing only zeros (*HYDROMEMBERCOEFF*) is assigned to every member. Here, the hydrodynamic influences on the turbine deflection due to the extra loading and on the eigendynamics due to hydrodynamic damping are omitted. In future campaigns, the hydrodynamic effects and the effect of flooding the tower will be thoroughly investigated and compared to experimental studies. Marine life form growth (*MaGrID*) and buoyancy (*IsBuoy*) are switched off. The maximum discretization size (*ElmDsc*) is set to 50 mm [58].

4.3 Constraints

The tower is supported by two 23024 CC/WW33 spherical roller bearings. The upper bearing (bearing 2) is fixed. Hence, the translation in \mathbf{e}_x , \mathbf{e}_y , and \mathbf{e}_z is constrained (coordinate systems as in Figure 4.4, g in \mathbf{e}_x). The bearings allow an angular misalignment of around \mathbf{e}_y and \mathbf{e}_z of $\pm 2.5^\circ$. The rotation around \mathbf{e}_x is free in the most recent design. The lower bearing (bearing 1) is floating. Translations in \mathbf{e}_y and \mathbf{e}_z are constrained. Additionally, the rotational brake is implemented at the lower bearing location. Thereby, the rotational degree of freedom (DOF) around \mathbf{e}_x is set to zero. The combination of both bearings defines the kinematics of the tower. The system's constraints are fed to QBLADE through the substructure definition file (*SUBCONSTRAINTS*, Appendix B.3). If not specifically defined, QBLADE's global coordinate system is used. A set of constraints can be assigned to any previously defined joint location. In the table, joints can be connected to the ground (*Ground*) or defined as transition pieces (*TrP*). Additionally, a joint can be connected to a second joint (*Jnt2ID*) or to a non-linear spring-damping system (*Spring*) [58]. The fixed DOFs are set by prescribing a 1 in the respective column of the table. The UBeRT substructure is directly connected to the nacelle. No tower definition is included in the design. Thus, the transition piece is located at the first substructure joint. According to the *SUBJOINTS* table, the bearings are located at joints seven and ten. The DOFs are assigned, respectively. Additionally, the anchor point of the stiffening rod could be fixed. Prospectively, studies could be conducted on the influence of the location of the anchor point on the eigendynamics of the turbine.

4.4 Validation and Verification

Tu et al. [94] distinguish between *validation* and *verification*. Validation refers to the comparison of results obtained from a simulation of a reference case with experimentally acquired data. The nu-

Figure 4.4: Reference tower model for validating QBLADE's structural beam model. Diameters: $D = 200$ mm, $d = 180$ mm. lengths: $L_1 = 1.559$ m, $L_2 = 3.568$ m. Derived properties: $A = 0.006$ m², $I_{yy} = 2.701 \times 10^{-5}$ m⁴. Mass properties: $E = 2 \times 10^{11}$ N m⁻², $\rho = 8000$ kg m⁻³, $m = 85$ kg, $g = 0$. Material: 1.4404 steel.

merical model is verified by comparing its results to an analytical solution. If no experimental data is available, a numerical model can also be validated against higher-fidelity codes or against already validated models. Due to the ongoing construction of the UBeRT structure, no experimental data exists yet. For this thesis, parts of the QBLADE model are validated employing the high-fidelity FEA solver SOLIDWORKS SIMULATION. QBLADE's estimations of the eigendynamics and the static deflection of the tower structure due to the design thrust are verified for a simplified tower model against an analytical solution.

The blade model is recreated in SOLIDWORKS from cross-sectional geometries. The three-dimensional FEA solver SOLIDWORKS SIMULATION is utilized to estimate the maximum blade tip deflection and the eigenfrequencies under distributed aerodynamic loading. The solver comprises an automatic meshing module based on tetrahedral elements. A curvature-adapted meshing option is chosen with maximum and minimum element sizes of 7.5 mm and 1.5 mm, yielding a total of 23893 elements. The same mesh parameters were used in MT1 [1] to estimate the maximum blade tip deflection imposed by the design loads. The SOLIDWORKS blade model weighs $m_{bl} = 4.82$ kg. The FEA solver predicts $f_{0,j} = \{81.5, 265.2\}$ Hz as eigenfrequencies for the first two out-of-plane (OOP) responses. The first in-plane (IP) mode is located at 373.42 Hz. The QFEM module [95, 96] in QBLADE allows the estimation of the eigenfrequencies of the blade. The first three natural frequencies of the blade at rest are $f_{0,j} = \{76.9, 253.6, 382.1\}$ Hz, where the former two flapwise shapes are dominated by directional responses in the OOP direction of the blade. The latter one is listed as an edgewise mode. IP and OOP mode shape components show comparably large amplitudes. The first torsional mode appears at $f_{0,7} = 2320.9$ Hz. Additionally, QFEM predicts a maximum normal deflection of $\delta_{tip} = 3.4$ mm at an inflow velocity of $\bar{U}_\infty = 2$ m s⁻¹ and TSR $\lambda = 9.5$. According to MT1 [1], SOLIDWORKS SIMULATION calculates a maximum blade tip deflection of 5 mm. The 32% error of QBLADE for the deflection and the deviations in the prediction of the eigenfrequencies are most likely caused by the reduced modeling fidelity of the structural beam model.

The structural tower model is verified by defining a reference case, for which an analytical solution exists (Figure 4.4). The length $L_1 = 1.559$ m is set according to the center distance between the 23024 CC/W33 bearings in the original tower model. $L_2 = 3.568$ m is derived from the free tower length of 3.402 m and the distance between the tower bottom node and the rotational shaft of 0.166 m. The outer and inner tube diameters are set at $D = 0.2$ m and $d = 0.18$ m to comply with the tower dimensions. The tube material is 1.4404 stainless-steel. A lumped mass of $m = 85$ kg equivalent to the complete nacelle assembly (nacelle, hub, blades) is placed at the end of the free tower length. The mass has no influence on the static deflection of the tower, as $g = 0$ is set. However, its influence on the eigendynamics of the reference model cannot be neglected. EULER-BERNOULLI's spatial differential equation (Equation (4.9)) relates the inner loads, i.e., the bending moment, with the curvature of the deflection $w(x)$. $\iota(\cdot) := \partial/\partial\vec{x}(\cdot)$ is the spatial derivative. $\rho(x)$ is the rotation angle. Integrating the

equation twice yields an undefined deflection curve for every point of the domain.

$$EI_{yy}w''(x) = -M_y(x), \quad w'(x) =: \rho(x) \quad (4.9)$$

For the model depicted in Figure 4.4, four boundary conditions can be identified (Equations (4.10)). Two running variables (x_1 and x_2) are required to describe the deflection and rotation in the entire domain.

$$w_1(0) = 0 \quad w_1(L_1) = 0 \quad (4.10a)$$

$$w_2(0) = 0 \quad \rho_2(0) = \rho_1(L_1) \quad (4.10b)$$

Including the boundary and transition conditions (Equation (4.10)) into the generic curves yields a closed solution for the deflection $w(x)$ and the rotation $\rho(x)$ of the beam axis (Equations (4.11), $B_{yy} := EI_{yy}$).

$$w_1(x_1) = -\frac{\mathcal{T}L_1^2L_2}{6B_{yy}}\left(1 - \left(\frac{x_1}{L_1}\right)^2\right)\frac{x_1}{L_1} \quad (4.11a)$$

$$\rho_1(x_1) = \frac{\mathcal{T}L_2}{6B_{yy}}\left(3\frac{x_1^2}{L_1} - L_1\right) \quad (4.11b)$$

$$w_2(x_2) = \frac{\mathcal{T}L_2^3}{6B_{yy}}\left(-\left(\frac{x_2}{L_2}\right)^2 + 3\left(\frac{x_2}{L_2}\right) + 2\frac{L_1}{L_2}\right)\frac{x_2}{L_2} \quad (4.11c)$$

$$\rho_2(x_2) = -\frac{\mathcal{T}L_2^2}{2B_{yy}}\left(\left(\frac{x_2}{L_2}\right)^2 - 2\frac{x_2}{L_2} - \frac{2L_1}{3L_2}\right) \quad (4.11d)$$

The model allows for calculating the static deflection imposed by a static load. The design thrust $\mathcal{T}_{\text{des}} = 2220 \text{ N}$, derived at $\bar{U}_\infty = 2 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ and $\lambda = 9.5$, causes a static deflection at the free end ($x^* = L_2 - 0.166 \text{ m}$) of $w_2(x^*) = 8.38 \text{ mm}$. The model is extended to derive the eigenfunctions and frequencies of the reference tower model. Again, EULER-BERNOULLI's time-dependent beam function is utilized (Equations (4.12)) for the two sections of the tower model (Figure 4.4). All structural and geometric properties (B_{yy} , $\mu := \rho A$) are assumed to be constant.

$$\mu\ddot{w}_1(x_1, t) + B_{yy}w_1''''(x_1, t) = 0 \quad (4.12a)$$

$$\mu\ddot{w}_2(x_2, t) + B_{yy}w_2''''(x_2, t) = 0 \quad (4.12b)$$

BERNOULLI's assumption states that the deflection $w(x, t)$ can be superimposed by a time function $T(t)$ and a spatial function $W(x)$ such that $w_i(x_i, t) = W_i(x)T_i(t)$, $i \in \{1, 2\}$. Including the initial function into the Equations (4.12) yields Equations (4.13).

$$\frac{\ddot{T}_i(t)}{T_i(t)} = -\frac{B_{yy}}{\mu}\frac{W_i''''(x)}{W_i(x)} \quad (4.13)$$

Equation (4.13) only holds true for every t and x for a constant γ , where γ is related to the angular eigenfrequencies by $\gamma = -\omega^2$ (Equation (4.14)).

$$\frac{\ddot{T}_i(t)}{T_i(t)} = -\frac{B_{yy}}{\mu}\frac{W_i''''(x)}{W_i(x)} = \gamma = -\omega^2 \quad (4.14)$$

The separation assumption allows finding the temporal and spatial solutions independently of each other. The time function $T(t)$ follows from Equation (4.15).

$$\ddot{T}_i(t) + \omega^2 T_i(t) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad T_i(t) = A_i \cos \omega t + B_i \sin \omega t \quad (4.15)$$

Equation (4.16) follows from the same procedure, where the dispersion relation $\mu/B_{yy}\omega^2 = \kappa^4$ is included.

$$W_i''''(x) - \kappa^4 W_i(x) = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \quad W_i(x) = C_i \cos \kappa x_i + D_i \cosh \kappa x_i + E_i \sin \kappa x_i + F_i \sinh \kappa x_i \quad (4.16)$$

The spatial Equations (4.16) are uniquely defined by including the system-dependent boundary conditions (Equations (4.17)). The deflection at both bearing locations ($x_1 = \{0, L_1\}$, $x_2 = 0$) must be zero (Equations (4.17a), (4.17c), (4.17d)). The left bearing and the free end are incapable of transmitting a moment (Equations (4.17b), (4.17g)). Additionally, the rotation and the moment at the second bearing must be continuous (Equations (4.17e), (4.17f)).

$$W_1(0) = 0 \quad (4.17a)$$

$$W_1''(0) = 0 \quad (4.17b)$$

$$W_1(L_1) = 0 \quad (4.17c)$$

$$W_2(0) = 0 \quad (4.17d)$$

$$W_1'(L_1) = W_2'(0) \quad (4.17e)$$

$$W_1''(L_1) = W_2''(0) \quad (4.17f)$$

$$W_2''(L_2) = 0 \quad (4.17g)$$

Eight boundary conditions are required to fully define the system of differential equations. Deriving the free-body diagram of the beam at the location of the lumped mass (Figure 4.4) relates the inner shear load $Q_2(L_2, t)$ and the inertia force of the mass $m\ddot{w}_2(L_2, t)$ (Equation (4.18)).

$$Q_2(L_2, t) = m\ddot{w}_2(L_2, t) = m\ddot{T}_2(t)W_2(L_2) \quad (4.18)$$

From Equation (4.9), a second expression (Equation (4.19)) for the inner shear load can be found.

$$Q_2(L_2, t) = B_{yy}w_2'''(L_2, t) = B_{yy}T_2(t)W_2'''(L_2) \quad (4.19)$$

Equalization of both equations yields the missing boundary condition (Equation (4.20)).

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{W_2'''(L_2)}{W_2(L_2)} &= \frac{m}{B_{yy}} \frac{\ddot{T}_2(t)}{T(t)} \stackrel{(4.14)}{=} -\frac{m}{B_{yy}} \omega^2 = -\frac{m}{B_{yy}} \frac{B_{yy}}{\mu} \kappa^4 = -\frac{m}{\mu} \kappa^4 \\ &\Rightarrow W_2'''(L_2) + \frac{m}{\mu} \kappa^4 W_2(L_2) = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (4.20)$$

The required derivatives of the initial spatial solution function $W_i(x_i)$ are listed in Equations (4.21).

$$W_i(x_i) = C_i \overbrace{\cos \kappa x_i}^{=:c_\kappa} + D_i \overbrace{\cosh \kappa x_i}^{=:ch_\kappa} + E_i \overbrace{\sin \kappa x_i}^{=:s_\kappa} + F_i \overbrace{\sinh \kappa x_i}^{=:sh_\kappa} \quad (4.21a)$$

$$W_i'(x_i) = -\kappa C_i s_\kappa + \kappa D_i sh_\kappa + \kappa E_i c_\kappa + \kappa F_i ch_\kappa \quad (4.21b)$$

$$W_i''(x_i) = -\kappa^2 C_i c_\kappa + \kappa^2 D_i ch_\kappa - \kappa^2 E_i s_\kappa + \kappa^2 F_i sh_\kappa \quad (4.21c)$$

$$W_i'''(x_i) = \kappa^3 C_i s_\kappa + \kappa^3 D_i sh_\kappa - \kappa^3 E_i c_\kappa + \kappa^3 F_i ch_\kappa \quad (4.21d)$$

Including the derivatives into the identified boundary conditions (Equations (4.17)) gives Equations (4.22).

$$W_1(0) = 0 = C_1 + D_1 \quad (4.22a)$$

$$W_1''(0) = 0 = -\kappa^2 C_1 + \kappa^2 D_1 \quad (4.22b)$$

$$W_1(L_1) = 0 = E_1 s_\kappa(L_1) + F_1 sh_\kappa(L_1) + C_1 c_\kappa(L_1) + D_1 ch_\kappa(L_1) \quad (4.22c)$$

$$W_2(0) = 0 = C_2 + D_2 \quad (4.22d)$$

$$\kappa E_2 + \kappa F_2 = -\kappa C_1 s_\kappa(L_1) + \kappa D_1 sh_\kappa(L_1) + \kappa E_1 c_\kappa(L_1) + \kappa F_1 ch_\kappa(L_1) \quad (4.22e)$$

$$\kappa^2 C_2 - \kappa^2 D_2 = -\kappa^2 C_1 c_\kappa(L_1) + \kappa^2 D_1 ch_\kappa(L_1) - \kappa^2 E_1 s_\kappa(L_1) + \kappa^2 F_1 sh_\kappa(L_1) \quad (4.22f)$$

$$W_2''(L_2) = 0 = -\kappa^2 C_2 c_\kappa(L_2) + \kappa^2 D_2 ch_\kappa(L_2) - \kappa^2 E_2 s_\kappa(L_2) + \kappa^2 F_2 sh_\kappa(L_2) \quad (4.22g)$$

For the free end (Equation (4.20)), inserting the derivatives of the spatial function $W_2(x_2)$ culminates in Equation (4.23).

$$0 = C_2 \overbrace{\left(s_\kappa(L_2) + \kappa \frac{m}{\mu} c_\kappa(L_2) \right)}^{(I)} + D_2 \overbrace{\left(sh_\kappa(L_2) + \kappa \frac{m}{\mu} ch_\kappa(L_2) \right)}^{(II)} + E_2 \overbrace{\left(-c_\kappa(L_2) + \kappa \frac{m}{\mu} s_\kappa(L_2) \right)}^{(III)} + F_2 \overbrace{\left(ch_\kappa(L_2) + \kappa \frac{m}{\mu} sh_\kappa(L_2) \right)}^{(VI)} \quad (4.23)$$

Altogether, these eight expressions form a homogeneous system of equations for the unknown parameters C_1, \dots, F_2 . Unique solutions to this system of equations exist if the determinant of the coefficient matrix $\vec{A}(\kappa)$ vanishes ($\det \vec{A}(\kappa) = 0$).

$$\overbrace{\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\kappa^2 & -\kappa^2 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ c_\kappa(L_1) & ch_\kappa(L_1) & s_\kappa(L_1) & sh_\kappa(L_1) & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ -\kappa s_\kappa(L_1) & \kappa sh_\kappa(L_1) & \kappa c_\kappa(L_1) & \kappa ch_\kappa(L_1) & 0 & 0 & -\kappa & -\kappa \\ -\kappa^2 c_\kappa(L_1) & \kappa^2 ch_\kappa(L_1) & -\kappa^2 s_\kappa(L_1) & \kappa^2 sh_\kappa(L_1) & \kappa^2 & -\kappa^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\kappa^2 c_\kappa(L_2) & \kappa^2 ch_\kappa(L_2) & -\kappa^2 s_\kappa(L_2) & \kappa^2 sh_\kappa(L_2) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & (I) & (II) & (III) & (VI) \end{bmatrix}}^{\vec{A}(\kappa)} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} C_1 & D_1 & E_1 & F_1 & C_2 & D_2 & E_2 & F_2 \end{bmatrix}^T = \vec{0} \quad (4.24)$$

No closed solution for the characteristic equation may be found. However, several numerical approaches for finding the roots $\kappa_{0,j}$ of the system of equations exist. The roots are related to the natural frequencies $\omega_{0,j}$ by the dispersion relation, Equation (4.25).

$$\omega_{0,j} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{B_{yy}}{\mu} \kappa^2} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{EI_{yy}}{\rho A} \kappa^2} \quad (4.25)$$

$$f_{0,j} = \frac{\omega_{0,j}}{2\pi}$$

For the tower model depicted in Figure 4.4, the first three eigenfrequencies $f_{0,j}$ are numerically searched for to compare the results to QBLADE's structural solver. The analytical solutions yield $f_{0,j} = \{6.96, 59.91, 182.48\}$ Hz for the first three eigenfrequencies. Note that only the eigenfunctions

in the $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_z\}$ plane are considered. The reference model of the tower is reproduced in QBLADE according to its cross-sectional and mass properties. The input files are provided in Appendix A. In the main file (Appendix A.1), the lumped mass is added as nacelle mass (*NACMASS*) and placed at the end of the tower. The tower-to-shaft distance (*TWR2SHFT*) is set to 166 mm (Figure 4.3). The blade number and the tower height are set to zero. The structural beam model of the turbine is defined in the substructure file (Appendix A.2). Only one element is defined according to the properties of the large 1.4404 stainless-steel tube ($D = 200$ mm, $d = 180$ mm, $E = 2 \times 10^{11}$ N m⁻², $\rho = 8000$ kg m⁻³, $G = 79$ N m⁻²). The bearings are incorporated by defining joints at their respective positions and by constraining the appropriate DOFs (Section 4.3). An external excitation at the hub in the global \mathbf{e}_x -direction is defined with a load equivalent to the design thrust $\mathcal{T}_{\text{des}} = 2220$ N and fed into QBLADE through an *External Loading File* (Appendix A.3). The load is fully applied at 0.5 s and held constant until 90 s. Between 0.3 to 0.5 s and 90 to 100 s, the load is linearly interpolated from and to 0 N [58]. The total simulation time is set to 1 s, such that the static deflection of the substructure under design loading can be extracted from the QBLADE simulation. QBLADE calculates a static deflection imposed by the design thrust of 8.25 mm compared to the 8.38 mm of the analytical model. Additionally, QBLADE's *Modal Analysis*³ feature is switched on for identifying the eigenfrequencies and eigenfunctions of the reference model. The tool performs a modal analysis at the end of the simulation, once the blades reach their initial azimuthal position [58]. Only side-side modes can be compared, as the analytical model is purely two-dimensional. The first two related eigenfrequencies appear at $f_{0,j} = \{7.13, 56.03\}$ Hz. For larger eigenfrequencies, the beam model appears to fail. QBLADE's structural solver reproduces the analytical solutions with high accuracy for the static and the dynamic cases. The negligible deviations from the analytical results can be explained by the different methods of setting up the beam model and by the discretization.

Additionally, the static deflection and eigenfrequencies of the more resolved representation of the UBeRT tower inside QBLADE are compared against a model in SOLIDWORKS. Again, no aerodynamic forces from the blades are included in the model. Only the blade and hub mass, together with the nacelle mass, is lumped ($m = 85$ kg) and placed at the end of the tower at a tower-to-shaft distance of 166 mm. The full structural representation of the substructure according to Table 4.3 is implemented (Appendix B.3). The influence of the connector flanges is modeled by placing mass points at their locations. The system yields a total mass of 387 kg. The same external loading file is used to excite the tower at the hub by the design thrust $\mathcal{T}_{\text{des}} = 2220$ N and to extract the static tower deflection (Appendix A.3). It sums to $\delta = 10.66$ mm at the end of the tower. The *Modal Analysis* tool in QBLADE is utilized to search for the eigenfrequencies of the system. The first four eigenfunctions are extracted to compare QBLADE's results to those of SOLIDWORKS. The correlated eigenfrequencies are $f_{0,j} = \{6.87, 38.95, 40.94, 90.27\}$ Hz. Mode shapes one and two are side-side responses of first and second orders of a regular beam model. The third eigenfunction is the same as the second one but in the fore-aft direction. The fourth shape is the side-side response of higher order. The substructure model, including the lumped nacelle mass, is reproduced in SOLIDWORKS and analyzed with its SIMULATION extension. The total system mass accumulates to 411.67 kg. A curvature-based mesh made from tetrahedral elements with maximum and minimum element sizes of 15 and 3 mm is generated. The total cell count is 131896. The design thrust results in a static deflection at the end of the tower of 11.68 mm. The FEA solver predicts $f_{0,j} = \{6.182, 6.183, 43.52, 43.59, 125.11\}$ Hz associated with the first five mode shapes. The first two are of opposite phases and molded by equal shares of side-side and fore-aft responses. The third and fourth eigenfunctions are likewise phase-related, yet of pure side-side and fore-aft nature, respectively. The fifth is a higher-harmonic version of mode number three. It must be assumed that additional pairs of eigenfunctions exist for higher frequencies due to the symmetry in the system. QBLADE and SOLIDWORKS estimate the same spectral locations of the eigenfrequencies, although the calculated mode shapes deviate moderately. The deviations can be explained by the different model masses, the varying treatment of the flanges, and the different shape of the lumped nacelle mass. Additionally, the fully three-dimensional FEA implementation

³Only available in the enterprise edition of QBLADE

utilized in SOLIDWORKS is assumed to deliver more accurate yet different results than a multi-body EULER-BERNOULLI beam representation. The results of the verification of the structural model representation are summarized in Table 4.4. QBLADE's structural solver is deemed sufficiently accurate while achieving high computational efficiency.

Table 4.4: Results of the verification of the structural model representation inside QBLADE.

Model	Validation	Results		QBlade	
	Method	Def. δ [mm]	Freq. $f_{0,i}$ [Hz]	Def. [%]	Freq. [%]
Blade	SOLIDWORKS	5	{81.5, 265.2, 373.4}	-32	{-5.6, -4.4, -2.3}
Valid.	Analytically	8.38	{7, 59.9}	-1.6	{2.4, -6.5}
Sim.	SOLIDWORKS	11.68	{6.2, 43.5, 125.1}	-8.7	{11.3, -8, -27.8}

5 Numerical Investigation

The UBERT model, including the substructure representation of the tower, is generated in QBLADE according to the input files in Appendix B. The numerical investigations of the model comprise an analysis of its structural properties considering aeroelastic effects (Section 5.1), uBEM simulations of the transient acceleration process and a quantification of the occurring loads (Sections 5.2), and LLFVW simulations of two operational points to provide insights in the development of the wake at different downwind locations (Section 5.3).

5.1 Modal Analysis

The modal response of the structural model of the turbine is investigated employing the *Modal Analysis* feature of QBLADE. The analysis starts once the turbine reaches its initial azimuthal position, i.e., blade one is pointing in the \mathbf{e}_z direction [58]. The frequency sweep begins at 0 Hz (*Search From Min. Freq. [Hz]*). Eigenfrequencies that are calculated to be less than 0.01 Hz apart are suppressed, as they are expected to be artificially created by the numerical representation (*Delta Freq. [Hz]*). The analysis of the non-rotating turbine ($n = 0 \text{ min}^{-1}$) reveals several tower modes within the operational regime of the turbine: two fore-aft modes at $f_{0,j} = \{6.56, 31.257\} \text{ Hz}$, $j \in \{1,4\}$, two side-side modes at $f_{0,j} = \{6.604, 35.87\} \text{ Hz}$, $j \in \{2,5\}$, and one torsional tower mode at $f_{0,3} = 24.86 \text{ Hz}$. Rotor modes can be identified at $f_{0,j} = \{67.827, 68.239\} \text{ Hz}$, $j \in \{6,7\}$, where the former is an asymmetric and the latter is a symmetric flapwise mode. Additionally, combined modes appear, such as a fore-aft tower mode with an asymmetric flap at $f_{0,8} = 86.249$ and a side-side mode with a symmetric flap at $f_{0,9} = 95.034 \text{ Hz}$. Due to the amplified added-mass effects in water, the eigenfrequencies are typically reduced compared to results obtained in air. For bodies made from slender steel pieces, a reduction of approximately 30% is yielded [97]. However, since all simulations of the structural response of the turbine are conducted without including the added-mass and additional damping effects of the surrounding water, this effect is omitted here. In the future, the QBLADE model could be enhanced by incorporating hydrodynamic effects. During the experimental testing of the turbine, a maximum rotational frequency of $f_{\text{rot,max}} = \lambda_{\text{max}} \bar{U}_{\infty,\text{des}} / (2\pi R) = 4.9 \text{ Hz}$ will be reached, where $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 10$ and $\bar{U}_{\infty,\text{des}} = 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. To identify critical operational points, a CAMPBELL diagram is created. uBEM simulations at a constant undisturbed inflow velocity of $\bar{U}_{\infty} = 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ with rotational frequencies ranging from $f_{\text{rot}} = 0.3$ to 4.8 Hz are conducted. The time step size is set to 0.002 s, yielding a constant sampling frequency of 500 Hz. According to NYQUIST-SHANNON's sampling theorem, frequencies up to 250 Hz can be accurately resolved. To assure that all higher structural frequencies are sufficiently damped, a digital low-pass filter of minimum order and with phase delay compensation introducing a stopband attenuation at 200 Hz is implemented in the post-processing. The azimuthal step of the uBEM simulations is set according to the time step size and the respective rotational frequency. It ranges from 0.216 to 3.456°. The ramp-up time for the structural initialization is set to 10 s to avoid the excitation of the tower. The overdamping factor is 100 for all simulations. In the turbine definition, PRANDTL's tip loss factor is included, whereas dynamic stall, the HIMMELSKAMP effect, and the tower shadow are omitted. Twelve polar sections are used for the azimuthal grid discretization. The blade is aerodynamically cosine-type discretized in 30 panels. 20 nodes are used to capture the structural response of the blades. Each simulation length is set such that the turbine performs 100 rotor rotations. The structural data is recorded after 10 s. An adequate convergence of the thrust coefficient with inter-time step deviations of less than 0.01% can be proven for all simulations. The nacelle accelerations \ddot{x}_N in \mathbf{e}_x (fore-aft) and \ddot{y}_N in \mathbf{e}_y (side-side) are investigated to reveal any resonant excitation of the tower and blade modes. Figure 5.1 shows the resulting CAMPBELL diagrams. On the y -axis, the rotational frequency of the turbine is plotted. At each RPM, the signals

Figure 5.1: CAMPBELL diagrams of the UBeRT: Nacelle acceleration **a)** \ddot{x}_N in \mathbf{e}_x (fore-aft) and **b)** \ddot{y}_N in \mathbf{e}_y (side-side). — Integer multiples of the rotational frequency f_{rot} . — Selected fore-aft (FA), torsional (T), and side-side (SS) modal frequencies of the tower.

($t \geq 10$ s) are transformed into the frequency domain employing the FOURIER transformation. The yielded amplitudes are plotted along the x -axis of the CAMPBELL diagrams. The z -axis visualizes the magnitude of the amplitudes. Typically, integer multiples (iP) of the respective rotational frequency appear in the FOURIER-transformed signals. Selected multiples are added to the diagrams (green lines in Figure 5.1). Additionally, the first two fore-aft (FA), side-side (SS), and one torsional (T) modal tower frequencies are plotted (red lines in Figure 5.1). The spectral representation of the turbine's fore-aft acceleration shows large responses along the 3, 6, and 12P curves (Figure 5.1a). Especially near the first fore-aft mode of the tower ($f_{0,1} = 6.56$ Hz) high amplification rates appear. This is not the case for the second tower fore-aft mode at $f_{0,4} = 31.257$ Hz and the torsional tower mode at $f_{0,3} = 24.86$ Hz. The same holds for the frequency content of the side-side acceleration of the nacelle (Figure 5.1b). The first modal side-side frequency at $f_{0,2} = 6.604$ Hz is located in the same spectral region as the first fore-aft mode. Large amplification rates can be observed for rotational frequencies between 1 and 2 Hz. Again, the torsional and the second side-side modes at $f_{0,5} = 35.87$ Hz cannot be identified in the depicted plot. The same applies to the rotor modes. Thus, they are not particularly highlighted. In general, only small acceleration amplitudes of up to 0.07 mm s^{-2} are revealed by the spectral analysis (Figure 5.1a at (5.4,1.8) in $\{f, f_{\text{rot}}\}$). This speaks for the successful structural design of the UBeRT test rig. However, an experimental modal and an operational vibration analysis during the commissioning of the test rig should be performed to gain clarity.

5.2 Turbine Acceleration

In MT1 [1], acceleration ramps of the tow carriage velocity \bar{U}_∞ and the RPM of the turbine n were defined to dimension the drivetrain components. Due to the limited towing tank length and to assure operational safety, the drive must be capable of accelerating the rotor even when the tow carriage is at standstill. Thus, the inflow velocity is ramped up after the rotor is accelerated. An analytical model was derived to estimate the drive train requirements. The full aeroelastic model of the UBeRT presented here allows a more detailed analysis of the loading. The uBEM theory is utilized to track the transient flapwise BRBM $M_{b,f}$ and the resulting flapwise blade tip deflection $\delta_{\text{tip},f}$, the generator torque \mathcal{Q} and the aerodynamic power \mathcal{P} , the turbine thrust \mathcal{T} , and the upper bearing force in thrust direction $F_{\text{ub},x}$ during the acceleration process. The ramps from MT1 [1] (Figure 5.2) are used as input to the QBLADE simulation by defining a *Simulation Input File* and

a *Hub Height File* (Appendices B.4 and B.5). Rather than prescribing an inflow velocity of 0 m s^{-1} for the first 16 s, 0.01 m s^{-1} is fed into QBLADE. Otherwise, the calculation of the TSR would cause unpredictable numerical behavior. In all scenarios, the undisturbed inflow velocity \bar{U}_∞ , i.e., the tow carriage velocity, is accelerated from 0.01 to 2 m s^{-1} , as it is the design inflow velocity. All related loads are expected to be maximal. All simulations are conducted with a time step size of 0.425 ms , an azimuthal step of 0.26° , and a simulation length of 40 s , yielding $94\,024$ total time steps. The ramp-up time is set to 1 s with an overdamping factor of 10 . PRANDTL's tip loss factor (Equation (3.8)) is included in the simulation. Dynamic stall is omitted, as no significant blade vibrations are expected. The tower shadow and the HIMMELSKAMP effect are neglected. The other simulation settings are left at their default values. The first acceleration ramp (Figure 5.2a) is related to the maximum RPM $n_{\text{des}} = 293 \text{ min}^{-1}$, derived at $\lambda = 10$ and $\bar{U}_\infty = 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. It was considered in MT1 [1], as it results in maximized loading during the initial drive state of the motor. The second ramp (Figure 5.2b) accelerates the turbine to the point of maximal power production ($n(\mathcal{P}_{\text{des}}) = 176 \text{ min}^{-1}$ at $\lambda = 6$, $\bar{U}_\infty = 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$), as suggested by the static BEM simulations (Figure 2.4a). Additionally, the operational point resulting in maximal torque (Figure 2.4b, $n(\mathcal{Q}_{\text{des}}) = 102 \text{ min}^{-1}$ at $\lambda = 3.5$, $\bar{U}_\infty = 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$) is considered to dimension the drive train components (shaft, bearings, coupling). In all plots in Figure 5.3, the turbine's transition from drive to generator state during the acceleration process can be seen in the blade loading (sign switch). The resulting loads resemble the analytically predicted requirements in MT1 [1] with only marginal quantitative differences. However, the accuracy of the uBEM results is questionable when the undisturbed inflow velocity is near zero. In this state, the turbine's wake is not convected which results in a strong interdependency with the flow state around the blades. Since the wake is not modeled in the BEM method, the prediction of the occurring loads will be inaccurate. Figures 5.3a and 5.3d show the acceleration ramp-related integral blade loads in the flapwise direction. The deflection strongly follows the trend of the bending moment. For $\bar{U}_\infty = 0.01 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, the blades deflect towards the undisturbed inflow direction ($\delta_{\text{tip},f} < 0$). Once the turbine reaches the generator state, the tip deflection and the flapwise BRBM become positive. The largest blade loads are imposed by the acceleration ramp to $n_{\text{des}} = 294 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Positive and negative deflections of more than 5 mm are reached. During the blade design procedure in MT1 [1], a FEA of the blade with a comparably large OOP loading was conducted. Minimal factors of safety of $\psi_{\text{min}} = 4.8$ were derived. Hence, for the dynamic loading during the acceleration process depicted in Figure 5.2a, the structural safety of the blade root connections can be guaranteed. The blade loads follow the imposed ramps, which suggests no significant resonant excitation of blade vibrations. Only for the acceleration ramp to $n(\mathcal{Q}_{\text{des}}) = 102 \text{ min}^{-1}$, small fluctuations in the flapwise bending moment and the deflection can be seen. This operational point coincides with large AoAs, imposing the risk of

Figure 5.2: Design travel profiles for the UBeRT. Tow carriage is accelerated from standstill to $\bar{U}_\infty = 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. a) Acceleration to the design RPM $n_{\text{des}} = 294 \text{ min}^{-1}$ ($\lambda = 10$, $\bar{U}_\infty = 2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$). b) Acceleration to $n_p = 176 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Point of maximum generator power $\mathcal{P}_{\text{max}} = 2.35 \text{ kW}$. c) Acceleration to $n_Q = 102 \text{ min}^{-1}$. Point of maximum generator torque $\mathcal{Q}_{\text{max}} = 186 \text{ Nm}$. Operational points derived from the steady BEM characteristics (Figure 2.4).

Figure 5.3: Design travel profile related turbine loads: (\blacktriangledown) ramp 5.2a, (\blacktriangle) ramp 5.2b, (\blacksquare) ramp 5.2c. a) Flapwise BRBM $M_{b,f}$ and d) blade tip deflection $\delta_{\text{tip},f}$. b) Aerodynamic torque Q , e) power \mathcal{P} , and c) thrust \mathcal{T} . f) Thrust aligned upper bearing force $F_{\text{ub},x}$.

stall. An unsteady response of the blades is therefore expected. An analysis of the frequency content of the tip deflection signals reveals a correlation with the rotational frequency of the simulation. Figures 5.3b and 5.3e show the aerodynamic torque and power demand and production during the acceleration of the test rig. The structural safety of the drivetrain components, such as the coupling and the shaft, is proven in MT1 [1] up to a torque of 200 Nm. The selected servo motor and the planetary gear are rated for a power output of 7.5 kW. As can be seen in the figures, the aerodynamic torque and power remain within the limitations of the incorporated drive train components. The maximum tower deflection and the fixed turbine bearing were assessed in MT1 [1], based on the design thrust $\mathcal{T}_{\text{des}} = 2220 \text{ N}$. Additionally, the maximum radial tower bearing forces at the upper and lower bearing locations were used for quantifying the minimum factor of safety (FOS) of the selected bearings (23024 CC/W33). However, Figure 5.3c suggests a maximum thrust during the acceleration to $n_{\text{des}} = 294 \text{ min}^{-1}$ of $\max(\mathcal{T}) = -2910 \text{ N}$ which exceeds the previously used design loads. Redoing the dimensioning of the bearings yields a reduced FOS for the higher-loaded lower bearing of $\psi_{\text{lb}} = 8.2$, based on a thrust-aligned radial force of $F_{\text{lb},x} = 9260 \text{ N}$. This is still considered enough for ensuring a safe operation. Additionally, Figure 5.3f depicts the upper bearing force in the \mathbf{e}_x -direction. During the first 2 s of the simulation, large forces appear in the sensor data. These are non-physical, as a very low inflow velocity of $\bar{U}_{\infty} = 0.01 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ and no rotational velocity are prescribed, resulting in zero thrust (Figure 5.3c). For the remaining part of the simulation, no further artificial signals are recorded. The trend of the upper bearing force closely follows the turbine's thrust. No significant excitation of natural frequencies and mode shapes is captured by the simulation of the acceleration process of the UBERT. Generally, the resulting turbine loads remain within the expected limitations without endangering critical components.

5.3 Wake States

Two LLFVW simulations are conducted at two operational points ($\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$: $\lambda = \{6, 9\}$) of the turbine to gain insights into the development of the wake as it is convected downstream. No high-fidelity CFD simulations or measurements of the wake are available. Hence, the obtained results have limited quantitative significance. Still, the simulations provide a data set that allows the testing of possible post-processing strategies, which will be important during the experimental campaigns. The wake is analyzed at the horizontal center lines of the rotor plane at ten downstream positions between 1 and $10D$. The wake is simulated up to a normalized rotor plane distance of $15D$ to assure sufficient convergence. The same structural turbine model as described in Sections 5.1 and 5.2 is utilized in the simulations. Table 5.1 describes the deviations of the LLFVW setup from the default values suggested by QBLADE. A detailed description of the parameters can be found in QBLADE's online documentation [58]. Most [91] extensively investigated the influence of parameter changes on the accuracy of the simulations when compared to high-fidelity CFD simulations of the International Energy Agency 15 MW reference turbine.

In the simulation, shed vortices are neglected (*Include Shed Vortices*). According to Equation (3.18b), vortices are shed when there is a temporal change in the strength of the bound vortex, i.e., a change in lift generation. Here, only results obtained from the converged wake are extracted, so only small temporal lift changes are expected. The vortex shedding would be of small magnitude and can therefore be neglected in the simulation to increase the computational efficiency [91]. The *Wake Relaxation Factor* of 0.8 is taken from Most [91]. The parameter

Table 5.1: LLFVW simulations: Turbine setup.

Setting	Value
Include Shed Vortices	off
Wake Relaxation Factor	0.8
Norm. Distance	15
Wake Reduction Factor	0
Wake Zones N/1/2/3	1/10/10/80
Initial Wake Core Radius	0.05
Turbulent Vortex Viscosity	10
Blade Panels	20 - Cosine

Norm. Distance is used to control up to which diameter-normalized distance the wake is simulated. The *Wake Reduction Factor* is used to filter out filaments that are smaller than the maximum vorticity in the wake multiplied by this factor. Typically, it removes shed vorticity from the wake that does not influence the wake dynamics, i.e., reduces the computational costs [58]. However, the value must be carefully tuned since it significantly affects the results of the LLFVW method. Therefore, it is set to zero for the two simulations conducted. In QBLADE the wake is grouped into four sections of increased coarsening. The parameter *Wake Zones N/1/2/3* controls the length of the individual wake zones in rotor revolutions. The input is taken from Most [91]. An *Initial Wake Core Radius* of 5% of the locale blade chord is prescribed. Cormier et al. [98] describe a semi-empirical model for the tip vortex aging process. It assigns an initial core radius of 5% of the blade chord at 93% span. The model shows decent accuracy when compared to a CFD simulation and in-situ measurements. The *Turbulent Vortex Viscosity* is used to desingularize BIOT-SAVART's law, as described in Section 3.2. The value is extracted from Sant [99], who suggests a value of 10 for small-scale HAWTs. The UBeRT blades are discretized into 20 elements with a cosine-type distribution to increase the modeling accuracy of the tip and root sections.

The selection of the two operational points $\lambda = \{6, 9\}$ with an undisturbed inflow velocity of $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ yields RPMs of $n = \{132, 198\} \text{ min}^{-1}$. The azimuthal discretization scheme is set to 2° . Most [91] suggests that 5° are sufficient to accurately capture the wake of the turbine. Due to the different geometric scales of the investigated turbines and the higher rotational velocities, the structural model shows an unstable response for 5° . Hence, the azimuthal discretization must be reduced to achieve computational stability. The rotational frequencies and the azimuthal discretization result in a temporal resolution of 2.52 and 1.68 ms. Data is recorded after 52s of simulation time. This is necessary for the wake to be convected to $15D$ when assuming an average wake convection velocity of $0.25 \bar{U}_\infty$. 25 rotor revolutions are simulated thereafter to gather a sufficient

Figure 5.4: Snapshots of the magnitude of the instantaneous velocity field $|\vec{U}(\vec{x},t)|$ in the wake of the UBeRT using QBLADE’s LLFVW module with an undisturbed inflow velocity of $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$: **a)** $\lambda = 6$ after 120 revolutions and **b)** $\lambda = 9$ after 180 revolutions, i.e., after 54.55 s for both.

amount of data for calculating the averaged velocity profiles. Depending on the rotational frequency, 7.58 and 11.36 s are necessary, culminating in a total simulation time of 65 and 60 s after rounding. The particle transformation of the wake is turned off. According to Marten et al. [51], the transformation of the vortex filaments into particles could improve the predictions of the LLFVW simulations if the onset of the transformation is triggered after the tip vortex breakdown. However, no means exist for validating the defining parameters. Additionally, the potential of increasing the computational efficiency of the simulations by the particle meshing is not exploited, as only two simulations are necessary for generating the desired sample data sets. Figure 5.4 shows two snapshots of the magnitude of the velocity field $|\vec{U}(\vec{x},t)|$ in the wake of the UBeRT. The horizontal extraction plane is placed along the center line of the rotor and spans $10D$ in downstream and 2.5 m in radial direction. The velocity components are computed at 1300×250 nodes. Green areas correspond to a velocity near the undisturbed inflow velocity. Areas in blue indicate low velocities; red ones show high velocities. The trailing filaments are displayed in black. In both figures, the induction of the rotor and its effect up to $10D$ downstream of the rotor plane can be seen. In the LLFVW method, the nacelle is not modeled. Instead, concentrated root vortices are induced by the spanwise circulation gradients (Figure 2.2b) of the bound vortex (Equation (3.18a)). This results in the generation of an artificial jet at the center of the rotor plane. The penetration length of the jet differs depending on the operational point. For both operating states, wake expansion compared to the swept area of the rotor can be observed. The magnitude of the increase appears to be comparable for both operational points. Figure 5.4a shows the UBeRT operating at $\lambda = 6$. According to estimations of the static BEM method (Figure 2.4d), this coincides with a maximized power output of the turbine. The center jet reaches approximately $1.5D$ into the low velocity regime behind the turbine. By comparing different time steps, wake meandering can be identified starting at approximately $5D$. Figure 5.4b depicts $\lambda = 9$, where the thrust coefficient reaches its maximum (Figure 2.4f). The center jet appears to be becoming increasingly stable. Its influence on the instantaneous velocity magnitude can be seen up to $5D$ downstream of the rotor. Generally, the wake seems shorter compared to the snapshot at $\lambda = 6$. This is consistent

with theoretical predictions. At higher TSRs, the distance between subsequent tip vortices is reduced, resulting in stronger unstable interactions. The wake breakdown is accelerated.

From the results of the simulations, the instantaneous velocity field $\vec{U}(\vec{x}, t)$ at $x^* = iD$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$, $-1.25 \text{ m} \leq y^* \leq 1.25 \text{ m}$, $z^* = 0.834 \text{ m}$ is extracted at 250 nodes per line. QBLADE's global Cartesian coordinate system is used. The z location accounts for the 1 m ground offset of the first structural tower node and the relative nacelle distance of 0.166 m (Section 4.2). Every tenth time step starting at 52 s is considered to reduce the amount of data to be processed. Figure 5.5 shows the normalized averaged velocity profiles $\bar{U}(\vec{x}^*)/\bar{U}_\infty$ for both operational points. The induction of the rotor reduces the velocity in the \mathbf{e}_x direction inside the wake to 33 % of the undisturbed inflow velocity. The gradual widening of the wakes is observed. Compared to the swept area of the rotor, which spans one diameter, the outer wake borders almost double. In the near-wake (Figure 5.5a), the varying signatures of the bound circulation distributions for both operational points can be seen. As the wake is convected further downstream, the rotor's influence becomes less apparent. No significant differences in the necessary recovery lengths can be observed in the data. After ten diameters, the low average velocity regions are almost fully compensated for. The artificial jet at the plane's center appears in the velocity profiles of both operational points. Their velocity magnitude and size are comparable. However, for $\lambda = 9$, the region reaches further downstream ($4D$, Figure 5.5d) than for $\lambda = 6$ ($2D$, Figure 5.5b), as expected from the wake snapshots. The latter could indicate an unstable root vortex. The level of generated turbulent fluctuations would increase, causing more efficient turbulent mixing with the surrounding fluid.

The fluctuations in the wake are estimated applying a numerical noise metric ϵ . For N velocity profiles, chosen according to the number of used time steps, sampled at radial location y_i , the metric is calculated from Equation (5.1). The numerator is the standard deviation of the instantaneous velocity field in the \mathbf{e}_x direction $U(y_i, t)$.

$$\epsilon_i(y_i) = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{j=1}^N (U(y_i, t_j) - \bar{U}_i(y_i))^2}}{\bar{U}_i(y_i)} \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.6 summarizes the fluctuation profiles at the same downstream positions that are used for the averaged velocity profiles. The expected differences between the two operational points concerning the center jet in the near wake (Figures 5.6a and 5.6b) can be observed. For $\lambda = 6$, the shear layers immediately generate large fluctuations. Whereas at $\lambda = 9$, the jet develops a far-reaching potential core. It is not until $4D$ downstream of the rotor plane that the correlated fluctuations reach the magnitude of the jet at $\lambda = 6$. $7D$ downstream of the rotor, both profiles converge to a common

Figure 5.5: Normalized averaged wake velocity profiles $\bar{U}(\vec{x}^*)/\bar{U}_\infty$ of the UBRT, where $x^* = iD$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$, $-1.25 \text{ m} \leq y^* \leq 1.25 \text{ m}$, $z^* = 0.834 \text{ m}$ and $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for two operational points: — $\lambda = 6$, — $\lambda = 9$.

Figure 5.6: Numerical noise metric $Ti(\vec{x}^*)$ in the wake of the UBeRT, where $x^* = iD$, $i \in \{1, \dots, 10\}$, $-1.25 \text{ m} \leq y^* \leq 1.25 \text{ m}$, $z^* = 0.834 \text{ m}$ and $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ for two operational points: — $\lambda = 6$, — $\lambda = 9$.

profile. After $10D$, the noise magnitudes are still at 10 % of the averaged velocity profile. The turbulent wake is expected to be detectable up to $20D$ behind the rotor, as suggested by the literature. The tip vortices induce shear layers that entrain the surrounding fluid, causing a radial expansion of the wake beyond $2D$ (Figure 5.6j). At downstream positions closer than $1D$ to the rotor plane, the radial wake enlargement approaches $1.25R$. In the design of the tower, the section connected to the turbine has a smaller outer diameter to reduce the tower's influence on the passing tip vortices. Its length of $995 \text{ mm} > 1.5R$ between the rotor's rotational axis and the flange where the tower's cross-section is increased appears to be sufficiently dimensioned to ensure a free radial expansion of the wake. Qualitatively, the fluctuation profiles derived at $\lambda = 9$ match the theoretical predictions. Most of the rotor-generated turbulence intensity in the near wake is attributed to the concentrated tip vortices. They shield the inboard region of the wake from the surrounding flow. Only after the breakdown of the tip vortices can the low-velocity region be properly re-energized by turbulent entrainment. The signature of the tip vortices can be traced between $1D$ and $5D$ of the fluctuation profiles obtained at $\lambda = 9$ (Figures 5.6a until 5.6e). For $\lambda = 6$, however, the very high numerical noise in the center wake region results from the unstable breakdown of the root vortices. This is artificially amplified by the modeling principles of the LLFVW strategy. The tip vortices appear weaker than at $\lambda = 6$ quantified by the generated noise magnitude.

The presented data set cannot be validated since no results from experiments or high-fidelity CFD simulations are available. Therefore, the accuracy of the results cannot be assessed. The selection of PIV planes based on the LLFVW results is not possible. However, the presented data captures general wake properties and can be utilized to develop and test post-processing schemes. In the future, the developed aerodynamic model could be quantitatively tuned using the results of the experimental UBeRT campaigns. Once validated, the model could be employed to run parameter studies on blade tip geometries, identify promising wake locations for extensive underwater PIV measurements, investigate occurring turbine loads, and test controllers.

6 Conclusion

This thesis presents means to reproduce the structural model of the UBeRT test rig in the mid-fidelity wind turbine simulation tool QBLADE. A simplified model is derived to verify the results analytically for the static deflection and the eigendynamics obtained by QBLADE. The reference model for verification purposes consists of a tube with constant cross-sectional properties, two constraints at the bearing locations, and a lumped mass at the end of the free length equal to the total mass of the rotor-nacelle assembly. QBLADE reproduces the expected tip deflection imposed by the design thrust within 2% accuracy. For the first two appearing eigenfrequencies, the deviations are within 7%. Thereafter, the original test rig model is recreated in SOLIDWORKS and analyzed similarly, employing the FEA solver SOLIDWORKS SIMULATION. The model comprises several profiles of changing cross-sectional properties, added masses to account for the connection flanges, the lumped nacelle mass, and matching constraints. In general, the results from QBLADE deviate more from SOLIDWORKS's predictions. The static deflection is underestimated by -8.7% . Comparing the first three groups of eigenfrequencies yields an overestimation of the first by 11.3% and a relative error of -8% for the second one. The inaccuracies of QBLADE's results can be explained by the modeling differences between the presented implementations. E.g., the FEA solver of SOLIDWORKS accounts for shear and three-dimensional deformations, which cannot be accounted for by the EULER-BERNOULLI beam model in QBLADE. The structural model of the UBeRT test rig is considered analytically verified and validated by code-to-code comparisons.

The structural model is employed to further analyze the turbine's dynamic response to external excitations. A modal analysis is conducted by operating the turbine at various rotational frequencies and constant inflow conditions. The side-side and fore-aft acceleration amplitudes of the nacelle are considered in the frequency domain. A CAMPBELL diagram is derived to identify resonant interactions and possibly damaging operational points. The first tower fore-aft and side-side frequencies at 6.6 Hz are amplified by integer multiples of the operational frequency. The 3 and $6P$ cause particularly strong interactions. The maximum acceleration amplitudes approach 0.07 mm s^{-2} . From the numerical considerations, no dangerous modes of operation can be detected. Final clarity will be gained during the commissioning of the test rig.

The acceleration ramps from MT1 [1] are implemented in QBLADE and analyzed employing the uBEM method. From the correlated transient turbine loading, an assessment of the FOSs of critical turbine components is redone, where necessary. All limits of the design-driving loads from MT1 [1] are complied with, except the thrust loading of the tower bearings. A reduced FOS of the higher-loaded lower bearing of $\psi_{1b} = 8.2$ is derived.

Additionally, an exemplary data set of the wake of the UBeRT model is generated using QBLADE's LLFVW module. Two operational points ($\lambda = \{6, 9\}$) at a constant inflow velocity of $\bar{U}_\infty = 1.5\text{ m s}^{-1}$ are considered. The wake is resolved up to $15D$ behind the turbine, of which the first $10D$ are further analyzed. Typical phenomena such as wake expansion, entrainment, and meandering are observed in the data. Means to quantitatively investigate velocity and fluctuation profiles at various downstream positions are developed. The velocity deficit, induced by the turbine's induction, is followed along the downstream coordinate. The mean velocity in the wake drops to 33% of the undisturbed inflow velocity in the near-wake. $10D$ downstream of the rotor plane, the velocity reduction is almost fully recovered. The numerical noise metric at $\lambda = 9$, induced by the generated trailing vortices in the wake, reproduces typical features of the turbulent fluctuations in the wake of HAWTs. In the near-wake, most of the turbulence intensity is generated by the coherent tip vortices. As the wake is convected, the correlated shear layers grow and entrain the surrounding fluid until they meet at the turbine's center line. Thereafter, the wake typically becomes GAUSSIAN. Even up to $20D$ downstream, the signature of the turbine can be found in measurements of the turbulent fluctuations. The generated data set is thoroughly assessed regarding its validity and quantitative quality. No measurements or high-fidelity

simulations of the wake of the UBeRT are available - yet. In particular, the inboard section of the rotor is distorted by the induction of strong root vortices. Depending on the operational point of the turbine, these vortices appear unstable in the immediate near-wake ($\lambda = 6$) or reach up to $4D$ downstream ($\lambda = 9$). Their occurrence in the wake is artificially enhanced by the modeling method of the LLFVW strategy. Hence, the generated wakes can only be used to test and tune post-processing strategies. No quantitative understanding can be gained from the generated wakes.

7 Outlook

To fully benefit from the UBeRT model, the main findings of the presented thesis should be compared against measurements. For the structural model, an experimental modal analysis in dry conditions of the blades and the tower should be conducted. The mode shapes and the locations of the natural frequencies of the test rig could be compared against the numerical predictions. Potential deviations should be addressed by further improving the structural model.

The characteristics of the physical turbine must be measured utilizing the incorporated sensors: a three-component gauge and/or the OOP BRBM for the thrust; the generator moment and/or the IP BRBM for the turbine torque; the rotational encoder and/or the once-per-revolution sensor for the rotor RPM. The static deflections of the tower and the blades could be assessed using the existing phase-locked digital image correlation system. Different blade pitch configurations should be investigated for the risk of blade surface cavitation and their influence on the turbine characteristics. Deviations from the predictions of the static BEM should be quantified. Potentially harmful operational points must be identified and assessed again.

Once velocity profiles in the wake of the turbine have been measured, the LLFVW module in QBLADE should be appropriately tuned to reproduce the wake at a wide range of operational points. This would significantly increase the efficiency of the measurements. Vortex criteria could be used to extract the tip vortex helix and identify unstable regions. PIV planes could be placed accordingly to avoid measuring the entire wake.

If the validation of the full QBLADE model is successful, the model could be extended to tackle additional research questions. Hydrodynamic coefficients can be assigned to the structural members. Thereby, added-mass and hydro-damping could be investigated. Comparisons to an operational vibration analysis would provide insights into the effects of submerging the turbine and parts of the tower. Additionally, the effect of flooding the tower members could be assessed. The additional stiffening member should be structurally accounted for, and its effect should be quantified. Ultimately, the structurally and aerodynamically validated test rig model could be used to conduct parameter studies of potential blade tip geometries and other tip vortex excitation methods before implementing them into the physical test rig. The QBLADE model has the potential to become a digital twin of the UBeRT test rig and would thereby serve the research on alleviating wake effects in modern-day wind parks at Technische Universität Berlin.

Bibliography

1. Krumbein, S.: Design of a horizontal axis wind turbine for experimental investigation in a large water towing tank. *Masterarbeit* (Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, 2023) (cit. on pp. 8, 14, 15, 30, 32, 39–41, 46).
2. Frandsen, S.: Turbulence and turbulence-generated structural loading in wind turbine clusters. *Dissertation* (DTU, Roskilde, 2007). <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/servlets/purl/20685756> (2023) (cit. on pp. 1, 2).
3. Pope, S. B. *Turbulent flows* 10. print. ISBN: 9780521598866 (Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, 2013) (cit. on p. 1).
4. Gasch, R. & Twele, J. *Wind Power Plants* ISBN: 978-3-642-22937-4. doi:10.1007/978-3-642-22938-1 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2012) (cit. on pp. 1, 10).
5. Burton, T., Jenkins, N., Sharpe, D. & Bossanyi, E. *Wind Energy Handbook* ISBN: 9780470699751. doi:10.1002/9781119992714 (Wiley, 2011) (cit. on pp. 1, 2, 16–18).
6. Manwell, J. F. *Wind energy explained: Theory, design and application* 2nd ed. ISBN: 9780470686287. doi:10.1002/9781119994367. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/book/10.1002/9781119994367> (Wiley, Chichester, U.K, 2009) (cit. on pp. 1, 18).
7. Barthelmie, R., Politis, E., Prospathopoulos, J., Rados, K., Schlez, W., Phillips, J., Neubert, A., Frandsen, S., Rathmann, O., Hansen, K., Cabezón, D., van der Pijl, S. & Schepers, J. Flow and wakes in large wind farms in complex terrain and offshore (2008) (cit. on pp. 1, 2).
8. Vermeer, L. J., Sørensen, J. N. & Crespo, A. Wind turbine wake aerodynamics. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences* **39**, 467–510. ISSN: 03760421. doi:10.1016/S0376-0421(03)00078-2 (2003) (cit. on pp. 1, 2).
9. Hau, E. & von Renouard, H. *Wind Turbines* ISBN: 978-3-540-24240-6. doi:10.1007/3-540-29284-5 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2006) (cit. on pp. 2, 17).
10. Lissaman, P. B. S. Energy Effectiveness of Arbitrary Arrays of Wind Turbines. *Journal of Energy* **3**, 323–328. ISSN: 0146-0412. doi:10.2514/3.62441 (1979) (cit. on p. 2).
11. Crespo, A. & Hernández, J. Turbulence characteristics in wind-turbine wakes. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* **61**, 71–85. ISSN: 01676105. doi:10.1016/0167-6105(95)00033-X (1996) (cit. on pp. 2, 3).
12. Sørensen, J. N., Mikkelsen, R., Sarmast, S., Ivanell, S. & Henningson, D. Determination of Wind Turbine Near-Wake Length Based on Stability Analysis. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **524**, 012155. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:10.1088/1742-6596/524/1/012155 (2014) (cit. on pp. 2, 5).
13. Ainslie, J. F. Calculating the flowfield in the wake of wind turbines. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* **27**, 213–224. ISSN: 01676105. doi:10.1016/0167-6105(88)90037-2 (1988) (cit. on p. 2).
14. Masters, G. M. *Renewable and efficient electric power systems* 2nd ed. ISBN: 9781118633519 (John Wiley & Sons Inc, Hoboken, NJ, 2013) (cit. on p. 2).
15. Herbert-Acero, J., Probst, O., Réthoré, P.-E., Larsen, G. & Castillo-Villar, K. A Review of Methodological Approaches for the Design and Optimization of Wind Farms. *Energies* **7**, 6930–7016. doi:10.3390/en7116930 (2014) (cit. on p. 2).

16. Mikkelsen, R., Sørensen, J. N., Øye, S. & Troldborg, N. Analysis of Power Enhancement for a Row of Wind Turbines Using the Actuator Line Technique. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **75**, 012044. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/75/1/012044](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/75/1/012044) (2007) (cit. on p. 2).
17. Barthelmie, R. J., Frandsen, S. T., Nielsen, M. N., Pryor, S. C., Rethore, P.-E. & Jørgensen, H. E. Modelling and measurements of power losses and turbulence intensity in wind turbine wakes at Middelgrunden offshore wind farm. *Wind Energy* **10**, 517–528. ISSN: 10954244. doi:[10.1002/we.238](https://doi.org/10.1002/we.238) (2007) (cit. on p. 2).
18. Dahlberg, J., Poppen, M. & Thor, S. E. Load/fatigue effects on a wind turbine generator in a wind farm. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* **39**, 199–209. ISSN: 01676105. doi:[10.1016/0167-6105\(92\)90546-M](https://doi.org/10.1016/0167-6105(92)90546-M) (1992) (cit. on p. 2).
19. Chacón, L., Crespo, A., Enevoldsen, P., Gómez-Elvira, R., Hernández, J., Højstrup, J., Manuel, F., Thomsen, K. & Sørensen, P.: *Measurements on and Modelling of Offshore Wind Farms* (ed Frandsen, S.) Roskilde, 1996. <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/servlets/purl/434951> (2022) (cit. on p. 2).
20. Widnall, S. E. The stability of a helical vortex filament. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **54**, 641–663. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S0022112072000928](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112072000928) (1972) (cit. on p. 3).
21. Gupta, B. P. & Loewy, R. G. Theoretical Analysis of the Aerodynamic Stability of Multiple, Interdigitated Helical Vortices. *AIAA Journal* **12**, 1381–1387. ISSN: 0001-1452. doi:[10.2514/3.49493](https://doi.org/10.2514/3.49493) (1974) (cit. on p. 3).
22. Bhagwat, M. J. & Leishman, J. G. Stability Analysis of Helicopter Rotor Wakes in Axial Flight. *Journal of the American Helicopter Society* **45**, 165. ISSN: 00028711. doi:[10.4050/JAHS.45.165](https://doi.org/10.4050/JAHS.45.165) (2000) (cit. on p. 3).
23. Joukowski, N. E. Vortex Theory of Screw Propeller (1912) (cit. on p. 3).
24. Boersma, J. & Wood, D. H. On the self-induced motion of a helical vortex. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **384**, 263–279. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S002211209900422X](https://doi.org/10.1017/S002211209900422X) (1999) (cit. on p. 3).
25. Okulov, V. L. On the stability of multiple helical vortices. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **521**, 319–342. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S0022112004001934](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112004001934) (2004) (cit. on p. 3).
26. Abraham, A., Dasari, T. & Hong, J. Effect of turbine nacelle and tower on the near wake of a utility-scale wind turbine. *Journal of Wind Engineering and Industrial Aerodynamics* **193**, 103981. ISSN: 01676105. doi:[10.1016/j.jweia.2019.103981](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jweia.2019.103981) (2019) (cit. on pp. 4, 5).
27. Hand, M. M., Simms, D. A., Fingersh, L. J., Jager, D. W., Cotrell, J. R., Schreck, S. & Larwood, S. M.: *Unsteady Aerodynamics Experiment Phase VI: Wind Tunnel Test Configurations and Available Data Campaigns* 2001. doi:[10.2172/15000240](https://doi.org/10.2172/15000240) (cit. on p. 4).
28. Schröder, D., Leweke, T., Hörnschemeyer, R. & Stumpf, E. Experiments on helical vortex pairs in the wake of a rotor. *AIAA Scitech 2021 Forum* (American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Virginia, 2021). ISBN: 978-1-62410-609-5. doi:[10.2514/6.2021-1088](https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2021-1088) (cit. on pp. 4–6).
29. Okulov, V. L. & Sørensen, J. N. Stability of helical tip vortices in a rotor far wake. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **576**, 1–25. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S0022112006004228](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112006004228) (2007) (cit. on p. 3).
30. Leweke, T. & Williamson, C. H. K. Cooperative elliptic instability of a vortex pair. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **360**, 85–119. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S0022112097008331](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112097008331) (1998) (cit. on p. 3).

31. Meunier, P. & Leweke, T. In *Vortex Structure and Dynamics* (eds Beig, R., Ehlers, J., Frisch, U., Hepp, K., Hillebrandt, W., Imboden, D., Jaffe, R. L., Kippenhahn, R., Lipowsky, R., Löhneysen, H. v., Ojima, I., Weidenmüller, H. A., Wess, J., Zittartz, J., Maurel, A. & Petitjeans, P.) 241–251 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2000). ISBN: 978-3-540-67920-2. doi:[10.1007/3-540-44535-8](https://doi.org/10.1007/3-540-44535-8) (cit. on p. 5).
32. Roy, C., Schaeffer, N., Le Dizès, S. & Thompson, M. Stability of a pair of co-rotating vortices with axial flow. *Physics of Fluids* **20**, 094101. ISSN: 1070-6631. doi:[10.1063/1.2967935](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2967935) (2008) (cit. on p. 5).
33. Meunier, P. & Leweke, T. Three-dimensional instability during vortex merging. *Physics of Fluids* **13**, 2747–2750. ISSN: 1070-6631. doi:[10.1063/1.1399033](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1399033) (2001) (cit. on p. 5).
34. Leweke, T., Le Dizès, S. & Williamson, C. H. Dynamics and Instabilities of Vortex Pairs. *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics* **48**, 507–541. ISSN: 0066-4189. doi:[10.1146/annurev-fluid-122414-034558](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-fluid-122414-034558) (2016) (cit. on p. 5).
35. Meunier, P., Le Dizès, S. & Leweke, T. Physics of vortex merging. *Comptes Rendus Physique* **6**, 431–450. ISSN: 16310705. doi:[10.1016/j.crhy.2005.06.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.crhy.2005.06.003) (2005) (cit. on pp. 5, 6).
36. Meunier, P. & Leweke, T. Elliptic instability of a co-rotating vortex pair. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **533**. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S0022112005004325](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112005004325) (2005) (cit. on p. 5).
37. Kerswell, R. R. Elliptical Instability. *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics* **34**, 83–113. ISSN: 0066-4189. doi:[10.1146/annurev.fluid.34.081701.171829](https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.fluid.34.081701.171829) (2002) (cit. on p. 5).
38. Leweke, T., Quaranta, H. U., Bolnot, H., Blanco-Rodríguez, F. J. & Le Dizès, S. Long- and short-wave instabilities in helical vortices. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **524**, 012154. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/524/1/012154](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/524/1/012154) (2014) (cit. on pp. 5, 6).
39. Schröder, D., Leweke, T., Hörnschemeyer, R. & Stumpf, E. Generation of a wingtip vortex pair using a pressure-side fin. *Aerospace Science and Technology* **130**, 107860. ISSN: 12709638. doi:[10.1016/j.ast.2022.107860](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2022.107860) (2022) (cit. on p. 5).
40. Fukumoto, Y. & Hattori, Y. Curvature instability of a vortex ring. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **526**, 77–115. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/S0022112004002678](https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022112004002678) (2005) (cit. on p. 5).
41. Hattori, Y. & Fukumoto, Y. Short-wave stability of a helical vortex tube: the effect of torsion on the curvature instability. *Theoretical and Computational Fluid Dynamics* **24**, 363–368. ISSN: 0935-4964. doi:[10.1007/s00162-009-0145-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00162-009-0145-2) (2010) (cit. on p. 5).
42. Blanco-Rodríguez, F. J. & Le Dizès, S. Curvature instability of a curved Batchelor vortex. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **814**, 397–415. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/jfm.2017.34](https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2017.34) (2017) (cit. on pp. 5, 21).
43. Quaranta, H. U., Bolnot, H. & Leweke, T. Long-wave instability of a helical vortex. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **780**, 687–716. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/jfm.2015.479](https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2015.479) (2015) (cit. on pp. 5, 21).
44. Quaranta, H. U., Brynjell-Rahkola, M., Leweke, T. & Henningson, D. S. Local and global pairing instabilities of two interlaced helical vortices. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **863**, 927–955. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/jfm.2018.904](https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2018.904) (2019) (cit. on p. 5).
45. Blanco-Rodríguez, F. J., Le Dizès, S., Selçuk, C., Delbende, I. & Rossi, M. Internal structure of vortex rings and helical vortices. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **785**, 219–247. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/jfm.2015.631](https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2015.631) (2015) (cit. on p. 5).

46. Blanco-Rodríguez, F. J. & Le Dizès, S. Elliptic instability of a curved Batchelor vortex. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics* **804**, 224–247. ISSN: 0022-1120. doi:[10.1017/jfm.2016.533](https://doi.org/10.1017/jfm.2016.533) (2016) (cit. on pp. 5, 21).
47. Ivanell, S., Mikkelsen, R., Sørensen, J. N. & Henningson, D. Stability analysis of the tip vortices of a wind turbine. *Wind Energy* **13**, 705–715. ISSN: 1095-4244. doi:[10.1002/we.391](https://doi.org/10.1002/we.391) (2010) (cit. on p. 5).
48. Brocklehurst, A. & Barakos, G. N. A review of helicopter rotor blade tip shapes. *Progress in Aerospace Sciences* **56**, 35–74. ISSN: 03760421. doi:[10.1016/j.paerosci.2012.06.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2012.06.003) (2013) (cit. on p. 5).
49. Buffo, R., Wolf, C., Dufhaus, S., Hörnschemeyer, R. & Stumpf, E. Vortex Creation and Wing-Tip Geometry Dependencies. *30th AIAA Applied Aerodynamics Conference* (American Institute of Aeronautics and Astronautics, Reston, Virginia, 2012). ISBN: 978-1-62410-185-4. doi:[10.2514/6.2012-2770](https://doi.org/10.2514/6.2012-2770) (cit. on p. 5).
50. Schröder, D., Leweke, T., Hörnschemeyer, R. & Stumpf, E. Instability and merging of a helical vortex pair in the wake of a rotor. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **1934**, 012007. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/1934/1/012007](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1934/1/012007) (2021) (cit. on p. 5).
51. Marten, D., Paschereit, C. O., Huang, X., Meinke, M., Schröder, W., Müller, J. & Oberleithner, K. Predicting Wind Turbine Wake Breakdown Using a Free Vortex Wake Code. *AIAA Journal* **58**, 4672–4685. ISSN: 0001-1452. doi:[10.2514/1.J058308](https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J058308) (2020) (cit. on pp. 5, 43).
52. Lyon, C., Broeren, A., Giguère, P., Goopalarthnam, A. & Selig, M. S. *Summary of low speed airfoil data* ISBN: 978-0964674714 (SoarTech Publications, Virginia Beach, Va., 1995) (cit. on pp. 8, 26).
53. Drela, M. In *Low Reynolds Number Aerodynamics* (eds Brebbia, C. A., Orszag, S. A., Seinfeld, J. H., Spanos, P., Cakmak, A. S., Silvester, P., Desai, C. S., Pinder, G., McCrory, R., Yip, S., Leckie, F. A., Pontor, A. R. S., Holz, K.-P., Bathe, K.-J., Connor, J., Wunderlich, W., Argyris, J. & Mueller, T. J.) 1–12 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1989). ISBN: 978-3-540-51884-6. doi:[10.1007/978-3-642-84010-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-84010-4) (cit. on pp. 8, 24).
54. Schmitz, G. Theorie und Entwurf von Windrädern optimaler Leistung. *Wissenschaftliche Zeitschrift der Universität Rostock* **5** (1955) (cit. on p. 10).
55. Glauert, H. In *Aerodynamic Theory* (ed Durand, W. F.) 169–360 (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 1935). ISBN: 978-3-642-89630-9. doi:[10.1007/978-3-642-91487-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-91487-4) (cit. on pp. 10, 16).
56. Payne, G. S., Stallard, T. & Martinez, R. Design and manufacture of a bed supported tidal turbine model for blade and shaft load measurement in turbulent flow and waves. *Renewable Energy* **107**, 312–326. ISSN: 09601481. doi:[10.1016/j.renene.2017.01.068](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2017.01.068) (2017) (cit. on p. 14).
57. Jentsch, M., Schmidt, H.-J., Wozidlo, R., Nayeri, C. N. & Paschereit, C. O. Challenges and procedures for experiments with steady and unsteady model velocities in a water towing tank. *Experiments in Fluids* **62**, 1–20. ISSN: 1432-1114. doi:[10.1007/s00348-021-03151-5](https://doi.org/10.1007/s00348-021-03151-5). <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s00348-021-03151-5#citeas> (2021) (cit. on p. 15).
58. Marten, D., Saverin, J. & Behrens de Luna, R.: *QBlade Documentation: Next Generation Wind Turbine Design and Simulation* (ed Technische Universität Berlin) Berlin, 2022. <https://docs.qblade.org/> (2022) (cit. on pp. 16, 19, 23–28, 31, 36, 38, 42).
59. Behrens de Luna, R.: Benchmarking of QBlade simulations of tip configurations versus HAWC2 on the IEA 10MW turbine. *Master Thesis* (Danmarks Tekniske Universitet, Risø, 2020). (2023) (cit. on pp. 16, 19, 23, 25).

60. Branlard, E. *Wind Turbine Aerodynamics and Vorticity-Based Methods* ISBN: 978-3-319-55163-0. doi:[10.1007/978-3-319-55164-7](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-55164-7) (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2017) (cit. on p. 16).
61. Hansen, M. O. L. *Aerodynamics of wind turbines* 2. ed. ISBN: 978-1-84407-438-9 (Earthscan, London, 2008) (cit. on pp. 16–19, 26, 28).
62. Behrens de Luna, R., Marten, D., Barlas, T., Horcas, S. G., Ramos-García, N., Li, A. & Paschereit, C. O. Comparison of different fidelity aerodynamic solvers on the IEA 10 MW turbine including novel tip extension geometries. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **2265**, 032002. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/2265/3/032002](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2265/3/032002) (2022) (cit. on pp. 16, 19, 22, 25).
63. Madsen, H. A., Bak, C., Døssing, M., Mikkelsen, R. & Øye, S. Validation and modification of the Blade Element Momentum theory based on comparisons with actuator disc simulations. *Wind Energy* **13**, 373–389. ISSN: 10954244. doi:[10.1002/we.359](https://doi.org/10.1002/we.359) (2010) (cit. on p. 19).
64. Bartholomay, S., Krumbein, S., Deichmann, V., Gentsch, M., Perez–Becker, S., Soto–Valle, R., Holst, D., Nayeri, C. N., Paschereit, C. O. & Oberleithner, K. Repetitive model predictive control for load alleviation on a research wind turbine using trailing edge flaps. *Wind Energy* **25**, 1290–1308. ISSN: 10954244. doi:[10.1002/we.2730](https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2730) (2022) (cit. on p. 19).
65. Bartholomay, S., Krumbein, S., Perez–Becker, S., Soto–Valle, R., Nayeri, C. N., Paschereit, C. O. & Oberleithner, K. Experimental assessment of a blended fatigue–extreme controller employing trailing edge flaps. *Wind Energy* **26**, 201–227. ISSN: 10954244. doi:[10.1002/we.2795](https://doi.org/10.1002/we.2795) (2023) (cit. on p. 19).
66. Henriksen, L. C., Hansen, M. H. & Poulsen, N. K. A simplified dynamic inflow model and its effect on the performance of free mean wind speed estimation. *Wind Energy*, n/a–n/a. ISSN: 10954244. doi:[10.1002/we.1548](https://doi.org/10.1002/we.1548) (2012) (cit. on p. 19).
67. Silva, C. T. & Donadon, M. V. Unsteady Blade Element–Momentum Method Including Returning Wake Effects. *Journal of Aerospace Technology and Management* **5**. doi:[10.5028/jatm.v5i1.163](https://doi.org/10.5028/jatm.v5i1.163) (2013) (cit. on p. 19).
68. Perez-Becker, S., Papi, F., Saverin, J., Marten, D., Bianchini, A. & Paschereit, C. O. Is the Blade Element Momentum theory overestimating wind turbine loads? – An aeroelastic comparison between OpenFAST’s AeroDyn and QBlade’s Lifting-Line Free Vortex Wake method. *Wind Energy Science* **5**, 721–743. doi:[10.5194/wes-5-721-2020](https://doi.org/10.5194/wes-5-721-2020) (2020) (cit. on pp. 19, 23, 25).
69. Van Garrel, A.: *Development of a Wind Turbine Aerodynamics Simulation Module* 2003. doi:[10.13140/RG.2.1.2773.8000](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.2773.8000) (cit. on pp. 19–22).
70. Phillips, W. F. & Snyder, D. O. Modern Adaptation of Prandtl’s Classic Lifting-Line Theory. *Journal of Aircraft* **37**, 662–670. ISSN: 0021-8669. doi:[10.2514/2.2649](https://doi.org/10.2514/2.2649) (2000) (cit. on pp. 20–22).
71. Spurk, J. H. & Aksel, N. *Fluid Mechanics* ISBN: 978-3-540-73536-6. doi:[10.1007/978-3-540-73537-3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-540-73537-3) (Springer Berlin Heidelberg, Berlin, Heidelberg, 2008) (cit. on p. 20).
72. Saffman, P. G. *Vortex Dynamics* ISBN: 9780521477390. doi:[10.1017/CBO9780511624063](https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511624063) (Cambridge University Press, 2012) (cit. on p. 20).
73. Katz, J. & Plotkin, A. *Low-speed aerodynamics* 2. ed. ISBN: 978-0-521-66219-2. doi:[031270](https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511624063) (Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, 2001) (cit. on pp. 20, 21).
74. Eloy, C. & Le Dizès, S. Stability of the Rankine vortex in a multipolar strain field. *Physics of Fluids* **13**, 660–676. ISSN: 1070-6631. doi:[10.1063/1.1345716](https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1345716) (2001) (cit. on p. 21).
75. Maslowe, S. A. Linear instability of a perturbed Lamb–Oseen vortex. *Fluid Dynamics Research* **54**, 015513. ISSN: 0169-5983. doi:[10.1088/1873-7005/ac522d](https://doi.org/10.1088/1873-7005/ac522d) (2022) (cit. on p. 21).

76. Marten, D., Lennie, M., Pechlivanoglou, G., Nayeri, C. N. & Paschereit, C. O. Implementation, Optimization and Validation of a Nonlinear Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake Module Within the Wind Turbine Simulation Code QBlade. *Volume 9: Oil and Gas Applications; Supercritical CO₂ Power Cycles; Wind Energy* (American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2015). ISBN: 978-0-7918-5680-2. doi:[10.1115/GT2015-43265](https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2015-43265) (cit. on pp. 22, 25).
77. Bak, C., Johansen, J. & Andersen, P. B. Three-Dimensional Corrections of Airfoil Characteristics Based on Pressure Distributions. *Proceedings of the European Wind Energy Conference and Exhibition*, 1–10. <https://orbit.dtu.dk/en/publications/three-dimensional-corrections-of-airfoil-characteristics-based-on> (2023) (2006) (cit. on p. 23).
78. Wendler, J., Marten, D., Pechlivanoglou, G., Nayeri, C. N. & Paschereit, C. O. An Unsteady Aerodynamics Model for Lifting Line Free Vortex Wake Simulations of HAWT and VAWT in QBlade. *Volume 9: Oil and Gas Applications; Supercritical CO₂ Power Cycles; Wind Energy* (American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2016). ISBN: 978-0-7918-4987-3. doi:[10.1115/GT2016-57184](https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2016-57184) (cit. on pp. 23, 25).
79. Marten, D.: *QBlade: a modern tool for the aeroelastic simulation of wind turbines* 2020. doi:[10.14279/depositonce-10646](https://doi.org/10.14279/depositonce-10646) (cit. on pp. 23, 25).
80. Crisfield, M. A. A consistent co-rotational formulation for non-linear, three-dimensional, beam-elements. *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering* **81**, 131–150. ISSN: 00457825. doi:[10.1016/0045-7825\(90\)90106-V](https://doi.org/10.1016/0045-7825(90)90106-V) (1990) (cit. on p. 23).
81. Zwölfer, A. & Gerstmayr, J. A concise nodal-based derivation of the floating frame of reference formulation for displacement-based solid finite elements. *Multibody System Dynamics* **49**, 291–313. ISSN: 1384-5640. doi:[10.1007/s11044-019-09716-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11044-019-09716-x) (2020) (cit. on p. 23).
82. Tasora, A., Serban, R., Mazhar, H., Pazouki, A., Melanz, D., Fleischmann, J., Taylor, M., Sugiyama, H. & Negrut, D. In *High Performance Computing in Science and Engineering* (eds Kozubek, T., Blaheta, R., ístek, J., Rozloník, M. & ermák, M.) 19–49 (Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2016). ISBN: 978-3-319-40360-1. doi:[10.1007/978-3-319-40361-8\underbrace{}2](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40361-8\underbrace{}2) (cit. on pp. 23, 24).
83. Jonkman, J. M.: *Modeling of the UAE Wind Turbine for Refinement of FAST_AD* Golden, Colorado, 2003. <https://www.nrel.gov/docs/fy04osti/34755.pdf> (2023) (cit. on p. 23).
84. Jonkman, J. M.: *Overview of the ElastoDyn Structural-Dynamics Module* Bergen, 2014. <https://dokumen.tips/documents/overview-of-the-elastodyn-structural-dynamics-background-elastodyn-what-is.html> (2023) (cit. on p. 23).
85. Wang, Q., Jonkman, J. M., Sprague, M. & Jonkman, B.: *BeamDyn User's Guide and Theory Manual* Golden, Colorado, 2016. https://www.nrel.gov/wind/nwtc/assets/downloads/BeamDyn/BeamDyn_Manual.pdf (2023) (cit. on p. 23).
86. Larsen, T. J. & Hansen, A. M.: *How 2 HAWC2, the user's manual* Roskilde, 2007. http://iis-03.risoe.dk/nethtml/risoe/publ_uk.htm (cit. on p. 23).
87. Montgomerie, B.: *Mehods for Root Effects, Tip Effects and Extending the Angle of Attack Range to +-180ř, with Application to Aerodynamics for Blades on Wind Turbines and Propellers* Stockholm, 2004. <https://www.osti.gov/etdeweb/servlets/purl/20607079> (2023) (cit. on p. 24).
88. Viterna, L. A. & Janetzke, D. C.: *Theoretical and Experimental Power From Large Horizontal-Axis Wind Turbines* Washington, D.C., 1982. doi:[10.2172/6763041](https://doi.org/10.2172/6763041). <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/6763041/> (2023) (cit. on p. 24).
89. Nayeri, C. N.: *FLOATECH: The future of floating wind turbines* Berlin, 2023. <https://www.floatech-project.com/> (2023) (cit. on p. 24).

90. Saverin, J., Peukert, J., Marten, D., Pechlivanoglou, G., Paschereit, C. O. & Greenblatt, D. Aeroelastic simulation of multi-MW wind turbines using a free vortex model coupled to a geometrically exact beam model. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **753**, 082015. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/753/8/082015](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/753/8/082015) (2016) (cit. on p. 25).
91. Most, S.: Comparison of Numerical Methods for Wind Turbine Wake Simulation. *Bachelorarbeit* (Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, 2022) (cit. on pp. 25, 42).
92. Steger, C.: *On the Calculation of Moments of Polygons* München, 1996. https://mv.in.tum.de/_media/members/steger/publications/1996/fgbv-96-04-steger.pdf (2023) (cit. on p. 27).
93. Deichmann, V.: Experimental Analysis and Modelling of the Structural Properties of the Berlin Research Turbine. *Bachelorarbeit* (Technische Universität Berlin, Berlin, 2021). https://www.s.tatic.tu.berlin/fileadmin/www/10005227/Abgeschlossene_Abschlussarbeiten/Bachelor/Thesis_Deichmann.pdf (2023) (cit. on p. 28).
94. Tu, J., Liu, C. & Yeoh, G. H. *Computational fluid dynamics: A practical approach* Third edition. ISBN: 978-0-08-101127-0. <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/book/9780081011270> (Butterworth-Heinemann, Amsterdam, 2018) (cit. on p. 31).
95. Lennie, M.: Development of the QFEM Solver: The Development of Modal Analysis Code for Wind Turbine Blades in QBlade. *Master Thesis* (Kungliga Tekniska högskolan, Stockholm, 2013). <https://kth.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:658391/FULLTEXT01.pdf> (2023) (cit. on p. 32).
96. Lennie, M., Marten, D., Pechlivanoglou, G., Nayeri, C. N. & Paschereit, C. O. Development and Validation of a Modal Analysis Code for Wind Turbine Blades. *Volume 3B: Oil and Gas Applications; Organic Rankine Cycle Power Systems; Supercritical CO2 Power Cycles; Wind Energy* (American Society of Mechanical Engineers, 2014). ISBN: 978-0-7918-4566-0. doi:[10.1115/GT2014-27151](https://doi.org/10.1115/GT2014-27151) (cit. on p. 32).
97. Stenius, I., Fagerberg, L. & Kuttenukeuler, J. Experimental eigenfrequency study of dry and fully wetted rectangular composite and metallic plates by forced vibrations. *Ocean Engineering* **111**, 95–103. ISSN: 00298018. doi:[10.1016/j.oceaneng.2015.10.047](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2015.10.047) (2016) (cit. on p. 38).
98. Cormier, M., Bühler, M., Mauz, M., Lutz, T., Bange, J. & Krämer, E. CFD Prediction of Tip Vortex Aging in the Wake of a Multi-MW Wind Turbine. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* **1618**, 062029. ISSN: 1742-6588. doi:[10.1088/1742-6596/1618/6/062029](https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/1618/6/062029) (2020) (cit. on p. 42).
99. Sant, T.: Improving BEM-based Aerodynamic Models in Wind Turbine Design Codes. *Dissertation* (Technische Universiteit Delft, Delft, 2007). <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Improving-BEM-based-Aerodynamic-Models-in-Wind-Sant/0c422d37d4682d9e843203fe6909a1fd4cf96354> (2023) (cit. on p. 42).

Nomenclature and Abbreviations

Roman

a	Axial induction factor
a^*	Tangential induction factor
c	Airfoil chord
D	(Outer) Diameter, without subscript: turbine diameter
d	Airfoil thickness, Inner diameter
E	YOUNG's modulus
f	Airfoil camber, Frequency
F_D	Drag force
f_D	Drag force per unit width
F_L	Lift force
f_L	Lift force per unit width
F_N	Normal force
f_N	Normal force per unit width
F	Force component
F_T	Tangential force
f_T	Tangential force per unit width
G	Shear modulus
g	Gravity
H	Depth
I	Second moment of area
i	Radius of gyration
L	Length
m	Mass
$M_{b,f}$	Flapwise blade root bending moment
N	Upper running variable for summations, ...
n	Rotational speed, without subscript: rotational speed of turbine; also running index/variable
N_b	Number of blades
Q	Inner shear load
q	Resulting absolute velocity
R	Radius, without subscript: turbine radius
t	Time variable
$\vec{U}(\vec{x},t)$ (e.g., $[U \ V \ W]_i(\vec{x},t)\mathbf{e}_i$)	Instantaneous velocity field
w	Deflection
\vec{x} (e.g., $[x \ y \ z]_i\mathbf{e}_i$)	Vectorial position in space

Greek

α Angle of attack

β	Blade pitch angle
Δ	Trailing edge thickness, Difference
δ	Distance, Wavelength, Deflection, Cut-off radius
ϵ	Metric for quantifying numerical noise
η	Natural profile coordinate in chord direction
$\vec{\eta}_{25}$	Quarter chord location
Γ	Circulation
γ	BERNOULLI constant
κ	Wavenumber
μ	Non-dimensional radius coordinate r/R , mass coefficient
ν	Kinematic viscosity
φ	Inflow Angle
ψ	Factor of safety
ϱ	Mass density
σ	Solidity
τ	Temporal discretization
θ	Temperature
ϑ	Blade phase angle
ξ_P	PRANDTL's tip loss factor
χ	Structural pitch angle
ζ	Natural profile coordinate perpendicular to chord direction
Ω	Angular velocity
ω	Angular eigenfrequency

Coefficients

C_D	Drag coefficient
C_L	Lift coefficient
C_P	Power coefficient
C_p	Pressure coefficient
C_Q	Torque coefficient
C_T	Thrust coefficient
λ	Tip speed ratio
Re	REYNOLDS number
σ	Cavitation number

Letter-like symbols

\mathcal{C}	Material curve
$d\vec{l}$	Vortex line element
\mathbf{e}	Unit vector
∂	Used to emphasize partial derivatives or the boundary of a surface or body

\mathcal{P}	Power, without subscript: aerodynamic turbine power
\mathcal{Q}	Rotor torque, without subscript: aerodynamic turbine torque
\mathcal{T}	Thrust, without subscript: aerodynamic turbine thrust

Subscript

aero	Aerodynamic (e.g., aerodynamic power)
at	Atmospheric
bl	Blade related
bnd	Bound vortex
des	Design driving quantity typically chosen a priori
elem	Elements in simulations
f	Flapwise
H	Tower hinge
hub	Rotor hub related
i	Running index/variable
∞	Free stream value at infinite distance
j	Running index/variable
k	Running index/variable
K	Tower stiffening knot
lb	Lower tower bearing
max	Maximum derived e.g., by means of maximum search
N	Nacelle related
0	Natural (angular) frequency
offset	Offset
red	Reduced quantity
res	Resulting quantity (e.g., resulting force)
rot	Rotation related quantity (rotational period, rotational frequency, ...)
S	SCHMITZ design approach
shd	Shed vortex
struct	Structural (e.g., structural deformation)
t	Thick airfoil subscript
tip	Blade tip related
T	Tower related
trl	Trailing vortex
ub	Upper tower bearing
v	Vapor

Superscript

$ (\cdot) $	Absolute of vector quantity
ind	Induced velocity from vorticity distribution

$\overline{(\cdot)}$ Suitably averaged quantity
 $\prime(\cdot) := \partial/\partial\vec{x}(\cdot)$ Partial component-wise spatial derivative
 T Transposed vector or matrix

Acronyms

AoA	angle of attack
BEM	blade element momentum
BRBM	blade root bending moment
CAD	computer-aided design
CFD	computational fluid mechanics
C_M	Moment coefficient
CNC	computerized numerical control
COG	center of gravity
DOF	degree of freedom
FEA	finite element analysis
FOS	factor of safety
GUI	graphical user interface
HAWT	horizontal axis wind turbine
IP	in-plane
LE	leading edge
LLFVW	lifting line free vortex wake
OOP	out-of-plane
PIV	particle image velocimetry
RPM	revolutions per minute
TE	trailing edge
TSR	tip speed ratio
uBEM	unsteady BEM
UBeRT	Underwater Berlin Research Turbine

Appendix A

Validation Input Files

Input files to QBLADE of the validation model.

A.1 „Main“ File

```
----- QBLADE STRUCTURAL MODEL INPUT FILE -----
CHRONO PARAMETERS -----
0.2 GLOBGEOMPS - Global geometry epsilon for node placement
-----
HAWT TURBINE CONFIGURATION -----
0.0 PRECONE - Rotor PreCone (HAWT only)
0.0 SHEP/TILT - Turbine Shaft Tilt (HAWT only)
0 OVERHANG - Rotor Overhang (HAWT only)
0 TWRESHFT - Tower to Shaft distance (HAWT only)
-----
MASS AND INERTIA -----
0.0 YAWRMMASS - Yaw Bearing Mass (kg) (HAWT only)
85 NACMASS - Nacelle Mass (kg) (HAWT only)
0.0 NACCMX - Downwind distance from the tower-top to the nacelle CM (meters)
0.0 NACCMY - Lateral distance from the tower-top to the nacelle CM (meters)
-0.166 NACCMZ - Vertical distance from the tower-top to the nacelle CM (meters)
0 NACYNMR - Nacelle Yaw Inertia (kg*m^2) (HAWT only)
0 HUBMASS - Hub Mass (kg) (HAWT only)
0 HUBINMR - Hub Inertia (kg*m^2) (HAWT only)
-----
DRIVETRAIN MODEL -----
12 GBRATIO - gearbox ratio (N)
0.95 GBOXEFF - gearbox efficiency (0-1)
false DETRDOF - model drivetrain dynamics (true / false)
0 GENINMR - Generator side (HSS) Inertia (kg*m^2)
0 DTTORSPR - Drivetrain torsional stiffness (N*m/rad)
0 DTTORDDMP - Drivetrain torsional damping (N*m*s/rad)
-----
BRAKE MODEL -----
10 BRKTRQQUE - maximum brake torque
0 BRKDEPLOY - brake deploy time (s) (only used with DTU style controllers)
0 BRKDELAY - brake delay time (s) (only used with DTU style controllers)
-----
SENSOR ERRORS -----
0 ERRORYaw - yaw error (deg) (HAWT only)
0 ERRORPITCH_1 - pitch error blade1 (deg)
0 ERRORPITCH_2 - pitch error blade2 (deg)
0 ERRORPITCH_3 - pitch error blade3 (deg)
-----
BLADES -----
0 NUMBLD - Number of blades
-----
TOWER -----
```

0 TWRHEIGHT - Height of the tower

UBerT_Substructure_Validation.dat SUBFILE - Name of file containing properties for the substructure

DATA OUTPUT TYPES

```

true FOR_OUT - store (local) forces at all chosen locations
true ROT_OUT - store (local) body rotations at all chosen locations
true MOM_OUT - store (local) moments at all chosen locations
true DEF_OUT - store (local) deflections at all chosen locations
true POS_OUT - store (global) positions at all chosen locations
true VEL_OUT - store (global) velocities at all chosen locations
true AOC_OUT - store (global) accelerations at all chosen locations
true LVE_OUT - store (local) velocities at all chosen locations
true LAC_OUT - store (local) accelerations at all chosen locations

```

DATA OUTPUT LOCATIONS

```

SUB_1_0.00
SUB_1_0.1
SUB_1_0.5
SUB_2_0.00
SUB_2_0.50

```

A.2 „Substructure“ Model Definition

0 WATERDEPTH

998.22 WATERDENSITY

false ISFLOATING

JOINTOFFSET

XPOS YPOS ZPOS

TP_INTERFACE_POS

X[m] Y[m] Z[m]

REF_OOG_POS

X[m] Y[m] Z[m]

REF_HYDRO_POS

X[m] Y[m] Z[m]

SUB_MASS

0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0

SUBJOINTS

JointID	JointX	JointY	JointZ
1	0	0	1
2	0	0	4.402
3	0	0	5.961

1 STIFFTUNER
1 MASSTUNER
1 BUOYANCYTUNER

SUBELEMENTS
 ElemID MASS E1x E1y EA GJ GA STRPPT KSX KSY RGX RGY XCM YCM XCE YCE XCS YCS DIA DAMP
 1 47.752 5401969 5401969 1193805208 4267555 471553057 0 0 0 0.34 0.34 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0 0.2 0.0024

HYDROMEMBERCOEFF
 CoeHTD CAN Cpn MGFC
 1 0 0 0

SUBCONSTRAINTS
 ID Jnt1D Jnt2D Trp Ground Spring DoF_X DoF_Y DoF_Z DoF_rX DoF_rY DoF_rZ
 1 1 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0
 2 2 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0
 3 3 0 0 0 1 1 1 1 0 0 0

SUBMEMBERS
 MemID Jnt1ID Jnt2ID ElemID ElemRot HyCoID IsBuoy MagrID FltArea ElmDsc Name Red Green Blue
 1 1 2 1 1 0 0 0 0.05 FreeLength 0 0 0
 2 2 3 1 1 0 0 0 0.05 BearingLength 255 255 255

TRANSITIONBLOCK
 WIDTH LENGTH HEIGHT
 0 0 0

TRANSITIONCYLINDER
 HEIGHT DIAMETER
 0 0

RGBCOLOR
 R G B
 255 200 15

A.3 „External Load“ File

HUB
 0 0 0 0 0 0
 0.3 0 0 0 0 0
 0.5 2220 0 0 0 0
 90 2220 0 0 0 0
 100 0 0 0 0 0

Appendix B

Full Simulation Input Files

Input files to QBLADE of the UBERT representation.

B.1 „Main“ File

```
----- QBLADE STRUCTURAL MODEL INPUT FILE -----
0.2  CHRONO PARAMETERS -----
      GLOBGEOMERS - Global geometry epsilon for node placement
-----
0.0  PRECONE - Rotor PreCone (HAWT only)
0.0  SHETTILT - Turbine Shaft Tilt (HAWT only)
0.4  OVERHANG - Rotor Overhang (HAWT only)
-0.166 TWRESHFT - Tower to Shaft distance (HAWT only)
-----
0.0  YAWRMMASS - Yaw Bearing Mass (kg) (HAWT only)
57.31 NACMASS - Nacelle Mass (kg) (HAWT only)
0.211 NACCMX - Downwind distance from the tower-top to the nacelle CM (meters) (HAWT only)
0.0  NACCMY - Lateral distance from the tower-top to the nacelle CM (meters) (HAWT only)
-0.147 NACCMZ - Vertical distance from the tower-top to the nacelle CM (meters) (HAWT only)
6.114 NACYNER - Nacelle Yaw Inertia (kg*m^2) (HAWT only)
13.04 HUBMASS - Hub Mass (kg) (HAWT only)
0.0179 HUBNER - Hub Inertia (kg*m^2) (HAWT only)
-----
      MASS AND INERTIA -----
12  DRIVETRAIN MODEL -----
0.95 GBRATIO - gearbox ratio (N)
false GBOXEFF - gearbox efficiency (0-1)
0  DTRDOF - model drivetrain dynamics (true / false)
0  GENNER - Generator side (HSS) Inertia (kg*m^2)
0  DTTORSPR - Drivetrain torsional stiffness (N*m/rad)
0  DTTORDDMP - Drivetrain torsional damping (N*m*s/rad)
-----
      BRAKE MODEL -----
10  BRKTRQQUE - maximum brake torque
0  BRKDEPLOY - brake deploy time (s) (only used with DTU style controllers)
0  BRKDELAY - brake delay time (s) (only used with DTU style controllers)
-----
      SENSOR ERRORS -----
0  ERRORXAW - yaw error (deg) (HAWT only)
0  ERRORPITCH_1 - pitch error blade1 (deg)
0  ERRORPITCH_2 - pitch error blade2 (deg)
0  ERRORPITCH_3 - pitch error blade3 (deg)
-----
      BLADES -----
3  NINBLD - Number of blades
UBERT_Blade.dat BLDFILE_1 - Name of file containing properties for blade 1
UBERT_Blade.dat BLDFILE_2 - Name of file containing properties for blade 2
```

UBERT_Blade.dat BUDDFILE_3 - Name of file containing properties for blade 3

0 TOWER
TWRHEIGHT - Height of the tower

UBERT_Substructure_Simulation.dat SUBFILE - Name of file containing properties for the substructure

	DATA OUTPUT TYPES
true	FOR_OUT - store (local) forces at all chosen locations
true	ROT_OUT - store (local) body rotations at all chosen locations
true	MOM_OUT - store (local) moments at all chosen locations
true	DEF_OUT - store (local) deflections at all chosen locations
true	POS_OUT - store (global) positions at all chosen locations
true	VEL_OUT - store (global) velocities at all chosen locations
true	ACC_OUT - store (global) accelerations at all chosen locations
true	IVE_OUT - store (local) velocities at all chosen locations
true	LAC_OUT - store (local) accelerations at all chosen locations

DATA OUTPUT LOCATIONS

SUB_1_0.00
SUB_2_0.00
SUB_3_0.00
SUB_4_0.00
SUB_5_0.00
SUB_6_0.00
SUB_7_0.00
SUB_8_0.00
SUB_8_0.50
SUB_9_0.00

B.2 „Blade“ Model Definition

0.0024 RAYLEIGHDAMP
1 STIFFTUNER
1 MASSTUNER
20 DISC

LENFRAC	MASSD	Elx	Ely	EA	GJ	GA	STRPIT	KSX	KSY	RGX	RGY	XCM	YCM	XCE	YCE	XCS	YCS
0	20.159	103633	103633	510351727	81870	0	0	0	0	0.25	0.25	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.0256	20.159	103633	103633	510351727	81870	0	0	0	0	0.25	0.25	0	0	0	0	0	0
0.0513	5.019	1139	39047	127071151	15874	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.0769	9.036	3707	127097	229254592	51668	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.1026	14.372	9337	320155	363857434	130150	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.1282	19.144	16570	568054	484669716	230926	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.1538	18.925	16191	555089	479106737	225656	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.1795	16.825	12798	438768	425959986	178369	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.2051	15.032	10215	350202	380548657	142365	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.2308	13.413	8133	278836	339566747	113353	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.2564	12.036	6549	224522	304705601	91273	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.2821	10.823	5296	181548	273998000	73803	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.3077	9.5811	4352	149195	248386950	60651	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.3333	8.87	3557	121952	224566371	49576	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.359	7.995	2890	99078	202413112	40277	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.3846	7.282	2397	82185	184351919	33410	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.4103	6.692	2024	69405	169412947	28215	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.4359	6.164	1718	58887	156048809	23939	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.4615	5.686	1461	50102	143938349	20367	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.4872	5.255	1249	42804	133043503	17401	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.5128	4.866	1071	36702	123196592	14920	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.5385	4.521	924	31674	114445761	12876	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0
0.5641	4.211	802	27486	106611688	11174	0	1.1026	0	0	0.0392	0.2298	0.0717	0.0211	0.0717	0.0211	0	0

```

0.5897 3.93 698 23940 99498369 9732 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.6154 3.679 612 20979 93142157 8529 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.641 3.447 537 18416 87267240 7487 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.6667 3.237 474 16241 81951404 6602 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.6923 3.044 419 14365 77072063 5840 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.7179 2.866 371 12731 72556338 5175 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.7436 2.703 330 11325 68435027 4604 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.7692 2.553 295 10101 64629765 4106 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.7949 2.416 264 9050 61173892 3679 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.8205 2.287 237 8109 57905924 3296 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.8462 2.166 212 7374 54843874 2957 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.8718 2.061 192 6581 52168886 2676 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.8974 1.964 174 5976 49710397 2429 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.9231 1.87 158 5418 47333921 22063 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
0.9487 1.785 144 4936 45179381 2007 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0
1 1.785 144 4936 45179381 2007 0 1.1026 0 0 0.0392 0.2298 0.0717 0.0211 0.0717 0.0211 0 0

```

B.3 „Substructure“ Model Definition

```

0 WATERDEPTH
998.22 WATERDENSITY
false ISFLOATING
JOINTOFFSET
XPOS YPOS ZPOS
0 0 0
TP_INTERFACE_POS
X[m] Y[m] Z[m]
0 0 1
REF_OOG_POS
X[m] Y[m] Z[m]
0 0 1
REF_HYDRO_POS
X[m] Y[m] Z[m]
0 0 0
SUB_MASS
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
0 0 0
SUBPOINTS
JointID JointX JointY JointZ
1 0 0 1
2 0 0 1.829
3 0 0 2.334
4 0 0 3.334
5 0 0 4.114
6 0 0 4.302
7 0 0 4.402
8 0 0 4.502
9 0 0 5.833
10 0 0 5.961
1 STIFFTUNER
1 MASSTUNER

```


B.4.2 RPM Design Power

Time	RPM
0	0.01
1	0.01
16	1.76

B.4.3 RPM Design Torque

Time	RPM
0	0.01
1	0.01
16	1.02

B.5 Hub Height File: Inflow Ramp

Time	Wind Speed
0	0.01
18	0.01
32	2
120	2